

Numerical Investigation of Black-Scholes Equation

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Abstract

Black-Scholes Equation provides a theoretical estimate for the price of options. In this thesis work, we consider both Linear and Nonlinear Black-Scholes Model for the European option price. We analytically approach the Black-Scholes Equation by the transformation of the problem into a forward convection-diffusion equation with linear and nonlinear term. We use Spectral Collocation Method and Differential Quadrature Method for Linear Black-Scholes Equation and compare the numerical results with the exact solution of the equation. Then the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation has been investigated. Here, different volatility models due to the presence of transaction costs has been considered. We use Finite-Difference-Method to solve the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation. Finally we present the numerical results of the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation. We use MATLAB for numerical implementation and LATEX has been used for the write up.

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Introduction

During the last several decades the trading of options and stocks has encountered a growing interest in both scientific work and everyday life. Fischer Black and Myron Scholes published a paper titled '*The Pricing of Options and Corporate Liabilities*' in 1973. They showed how the pricing of options is uniquely determined by their formula. After their publication of this paper, the formula was named after them. The arbitrage reasoning method was used in their paper which was developed by Robert Merton. They were given the Nobel prize in 1997 for this Option Pricing model.

This Black-Scholes Model (BSM) was the first model for pricing options. After this model, there were more models developed by the mathematicians to estimate stock option price. There are some limitations to the BSM. That is why the classical model sometimes differ with the realistic price of the options [3, 44]. There had been numerous attempts on improving the BSM [28, 35]. In the Linear BSM, the volatility (*the standard deviation of the stock prices*) is assumed to be constant. This assumption is not realistic. That is why in the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Model (NBSM), the volatility term is not constant. Therefore, NBSM is less error prone than the linear one. There have been various schemes used to solve BSM. If one wants to solve an ODE or PDE to high accuracy on a simple domain, and if the data defining the problem are smooth, then spectral methods are usually the best tool [67]. This method has the ability to achieve ten digits of accuracy where a finite difference scheme would get two or three. This method demands less computer memory than the alternatives and was developed by Steven Orszag in 1969. Lloyd N. Trefethen's book named "*Spectral Methods in MATLAB*" provides fundamental ideas and techniques of spectral methods. This book offers a remarkable range of ODE and PDE problems which can be

solved to high precision in MATLAB. We use the ideas from this book to implement spectral method in BSM.

The differential quadrature method is a numerical solution technique for initial and boundary problems. It was developed by the late Richard Bellman and his associates in the early 70s and, since then, the technique has been successfully employed in a variety of problems in engineering and physical sciences. The method has been projected by its proponents as a potential alternative to the conventional numerical solution techniques such as the finite difference and finite element methods. Ram Jiware [45] provided adequate details about this method. We numerically solve BSM using this method.

Over the last two decades, the NBSM has become an interest topic to the mathematicians. Because NBSM provides better and more accurate option price results than the BSM [38]. The reason behind this accuracy is taking more realistic assumptions such as illiquid markets, risk from an unprotected portfolio or large investors, transaction costs. This assumptions has a impact on the volatility, stock price and the option price. During [24] showed the theoretical basis of NBSM and provided some mathematical analysis. He also laid down the groundwork for numerically solving the NBSM using finite-difference method. Ankudinova [2] went further using During's theoretical basis[24] to numerically approximate the NBSM. She converted a system of algebraic equations (finite difference scheme) described in During's paper into a Matricies. Strikwerda [70] provided the stability range for the parameters that were used in the Finite-difference scheme. We use all these details to numerically investigate NBSM.

Our dissertation is based on the BSM of option pricing. Black-Scholes equation is a partial differential equation dependent on two independent variables [73]. Our thesis has two major parts, firstly our work is focused on Linear BSM; Whereas in the second part, we gave full emphasis on the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation. In

the part of Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation, we investigate several reasons for the nonlinearity. We mainly focus on the nonlinearity resulting from a modified volatility function due to transaction costs [2]. We give a review of Black-Scholes Equation for European Options and the numerical schemes for the solution.

We start by the introduction of the norms of financial mathematics in the **Chapter one**. And a brief review of the Black-Scholes Equation [19, 39, 65].

In **Chapter two**, we have given a detailed analytical solution of Linear Black-Scholes Equation. We solve the classical Black-Scholes Equation to get the exact solution [22, 69]. This exact solution is the standard to which we measure both the linear and nonlinear solutions that we approximate using numerical schemes.

Chapter three has a brief discussion about the Spectral Collocation Method. We get the idea of the Chebyshev differentiation Matrix. Using this Matrix we solve the Linear Black-Scholes Equation [31, 72, 6].

In **Chapter four**, we give a short description about differential quadrature method [9]. This chapter has similarities with the Spectral Collocation chapter. Again, we use a matrix called differential quadrature matrix to solve the classical Black-Scholes Equation.

In **Chapter five**, we introduce the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation. We give different reasons behind the nonlinearity [?, 32, 24, 35]. And some volatility models are written in this chapter. We have given short descriptions to the volatility models too.

Chapter six has a short but efficient analytical solution of Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation. We use Finite Difference Method (FDM) [18, 17, 37, 70] to solve the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation.

In **Chapter seven**, we present an idea of fractional Black-Scholes Equation [40, 54, 58]. We do not have enough time to explore this field thoroughly, leaving this for the future work.

We end the thesis with a conclusion and future directions in chapter seven.

Chapter 1

Black Scholes Equation

1.1 Introduction

Black-Scholes Equation is a distinguished option pricing model in financial mathematics. M.Scholes, F.Black and R.Merton developed the *Black-Scholes* model in 1973 and stands as one of the most important concepts in modern financial theory. This eventually led them to win a Nobel prize in Economy in 1997 [65]. This model has a huge impact on stock market. And it helps the owner of the stock to have the authority to make decisions about buying or selling. There were some studies that show that Black-Scholes model produces option Prices which are very close to the exact price at which they were exchanged. Even if there are few limitations to this, the *Black-Scholes* model exhibits a great deal of contribution to the stock markets and options. It is a financial tool which is extensively used on stock market.

1.2 Financial Derivatives

It is a security for which the value is dependent on the value of a more fundamental underlying asset [73]. The standard variables of financial derivatives which are also known as *contingent* claims are price of the exchanged asset, interest rate and so on. We can use the Contingent claims to reduce the losses generated by the fluctuations of price of the underlying asset. Now, this protection procedure is called *hedging* [3]. In this dissertation our focus is on European call and put options.

1.3 Option Price

Option price is a financial derivative which is defined as,

Definition: *It is a contract that offers the authority to the owner but does not give the agreement to sell or buy an asset for a fixed price at a certain time in the future [73].*

Therefore, options are reviewed as the process of a *protection* against troublesome movements of the price. The options owner has to reimburse a payment called premium by which they have the opportunity to enter into the option contract. Conversely in a *forward contract* there is no fee. (*forward contract:* A forward contract is a settlement between two affiliations that one of them will buy an asset on a fix time for a predetermined price from the other affiliation)

The predetermined or fixed price is called the Strike price or Exercise price and it is denoted by K or E . The *certain time* or fixed time is called the maturity time or expiration time. It is denoted by T . We have two kinds of Options:

1. **Call Option:** The possessor has the authority to purchase the underlying asset.
2. **Put Option:** The possessor has the authority to sell the underlying asset.

At the maturity time T , there are three different classes of end result for the asset price $S(T)$ [73]:

- $S(T) > K$, at this class, the owner can buy the asset for the strike price K which is beneath the present price. He has the opportunity to sell the asset immediately at the price $S(T)$. He will secure $(S(T) - K)$ which is positive. And this kind of option is known as **in the money option**.
- $S(T) = K$, in this case there is no gain in selling the option as there is zero profit. This is known as **at the money option**.
- $S(T) < K$, there is not only no profit in this case but also loss. This is known as **out the money option**.

The Stock Option price is influenced by the following factors [73]:

1. Present stock price (S_0).
2. The Exercise or strike price (K).
3. Time to expiration(maturity) $T - t$.
4. The volatility of the stock price (σ).
5. The risk-less interest rate (r).
6. Dividends anticipated during the life time of the option.

There are two major approaches for pricing real options which are continuous time model and discrete time model. Our disseration is established on Black-Scholes continuous time model.

1.3.1 Classification of Option Price

Principally there are three types of Option Price:

- **European Option:** This option can be practiced only at the expiration date of the option, i.e. at the fixed time.
- **American Option:** It can be practiced at any time before the expiration date or maturity time.
- **Asian Option:** It is the class of option where the payment function is dependent on the average price of the underlying asset over the fixed period of time. Whereas the standard options European and American , the pay off is dependent on the price of the underlying asset at a fixed time(maturity). So this option is also known as *Average Option*. The developers of this pricing model were in Tokyo when they created the pricing model. Therefore, the name *Asian Option*.

1.3.2 European Option

European Call Option is a contract between two parties where at a fixed time in the future, called expiration date or maturity T , the possessor of the option may buy an asset known as the underlying asset $S(t)$, for a fixed price called the strike or exercise price K . The other party has the agreement to sell the asset if the possessor wishes to buy it.

We have already discussed about the three cases for Options. From them we can easily deduce that the value of the European Call option at expiry, called the pay-off function:

$$V(S, T) = \max(S - K, 0).$$

Figure 1.1: European Call Option Price $V(S, t)$ at strike price $K = 100$

European Put Option is the authority to sell the underlying asset $S(t)$ at the maturity date T for the strike price K .

The pay-off function for European Put Option is:

$$V(S, T) = \max(K - S, 0).$$

Figure 1.2: European Put Option Price $V(S, t)$ at strike price $K = 100$

1.4 Black-Scholes Equation

In the Inception of the 1970's Fisher Black, Myron Scholes and Robert Merton developed the classical Black-Scholes Equation(*PDE*). It was a quintessential advancement in the field of quantitative finance. There are two classes of **Black-Scholes** PDE which are Linear and Nonlinear. Classical model always refers to linear Black-Scholes Equation. The Black-Scholes PDE is dependent on two independent variables which are time t and Stock price $S(t)$. The Black-Scholes PDE is of the parabolic form. It is called the backward parabolic form because of the presence of having the opposite sign on the second derivative. There are some assumptions involved in Black-Scholes PDE. As well as ,there are some limitations in this option pricing model.

In this work, we reduce the Black-Scholes PDE into heat equation. Then we use numerical schemes to solve it.

1.5 Limitations of Black-Scholes Equation

There are some limitations of **Black-Scholes** model because of some assumptions [4,7]:

- Throughout the option's lifetime, the stock pays **no dividends**.

But in reality most of the enterprises give the payment of dividends to their share holder. Therefore, this is a significant constraint to the model.

- There are no commissions charged in this model.

Usually the participants of the market have to pay a commission to buy or sell options. Even floor traders have to pay a small fee. The commission paid by the individual trader's is more significant which can sometimes deform the outcome of the Black-Scholes Model.

- Interest rate and volatility are known and constant.
- The trading of assets is a continuous process.
- Transaction costs are ignored.
- Normal distribution is followed for underlying asset price.
- It assumes that options has the similar properties of the European option price.

1.6 Derivation of Black Scholes Equation By Hedging argument

We generally presume that the *asset price* $S(t)$ always follows a Geometric Brownian motion:

$$dS = \mu S dt + \sigma S dW.$$

$$\text{or } dS = S(\mu dt + \sigma dW).$$

$$\text{or } \frac{dS}{S} = \mu dt + \sigma dW.$$

where W is the stochastic variable. W and dW operate as unpredictability in stock market. And μdt works as the expected value whereas $\sigma^2 dt$ is the variance.

From Ito's Lemma, we can write:

$$dV = \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + \mu S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} \right) dt + \sigma S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} dW.$$

We can rewrite this as:

$$\Delta V = \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + \mu S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} \right) \Delta t + \sigma S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} \Delta W.$$

We can rewrite $dS = \mu S dt + \sigma S dW$ this as:

$$\Delta S = \mu S \Delta t + \sigma S \Delta W$$

Then we are going to construct a portfolio Π which can be self financed. This portfolio is composed of an amount Δ of the underlying stock, such that the portfolio is riskless and one option [62, 19, 10]. Therefore, the value of the portfolio at time t is

$$\Pi(t) = V(t) + \Delta S(t). \quad (1.1)$$

Hence we can write,

$$d\Pi = dV + \Delta dS \quad (1.2)$$

$$= \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \mu S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + \Delta \mu S \right) dt + (\sigma S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} + \Delta \sigma S) dW. \quad (1.3)$$

There are two properties of the portfolio. The first property states that it must risk-free which indicates that the 2nd term involving the Brownian Motion dW is zero, so that

$$\sigma S \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} + \Delta \sigma S = 0,$$

which becomes

$$\Delta = -\frac{\partial V}{\partial S}.$$

Now we can Substitute Δ in Equation (1.2) to get

$$d\Pi = \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2}.$$

The second property is that the portfolio has to obtain the risk free rate.

$$d\Pi = r\Pi dt \quad (1.4)$$

$$= \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} \right) dt = r \left(V - \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} S \right) dt \quad (1.5)$$

We can easily rearrange (1.5) to get

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + rS \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} - rV = 0.$$

This is called the Black-Scholes Partial Differential Equation.

1.7 Derivation of Black-Scholes Equation by Binomial Model

The stock price at the time t is S_t defined as,

$$u = \exp^{\sigma\sqrt{dt}}$$

At the time $t + dt$ the the stock price goes up to $S_{t+dt}^u = uS_t$, having the probability

$$p = \frac{\exp^{rdt} - d}{u - d}$$

The derivative has risk-less value which gives a relation [19],

$$V \exp^{rdt} = pV_u + (1 - p)V_d = p(V_u - Vd) + Vd. \quad (1.6)$$

where $V = V(S_t)$, $V_u = V(S_{t+dt}^u)$ and $V_d = V(S_{t+dt}^d)$.

Now we will use Taylor series expansions of V_u , V_d , \exp^{rdt} , u and d up to order dt .

From Taylor series we have,

$$V_u \approx V + \frac{\partial V}{\partial S}(S_{t+dt}^u - S_t) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2}(S_{t+dt}^u - S_t)^2 + \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} dt \quad (1.7)$$

$$= V + \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} S_t (u - 1) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} S_t^2 (u - 1)^2 + \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} dt. \quad (1.8)$$

We similarly get,

$$V_d \approx V + \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} S_t (d - 1) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} S_t^2 (d - 1)^2 + \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} dt. \quad (1.9)$$

The other expansions are

$$\exp^{rdt} \approx 1 + rdt$$

$$u \approx 1 + \sigma\sqrt{dt} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 dt$$

$$d \approx 1 - \sigma\sqrt{dt} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 dt$$

Here we have $(u - 1)^2 = (d - 1)^2 = \sigma^2 dt$. From which, we can write

$$p(V_u - Vd) = p(u - d) \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} S_t \quad (1.10)$$

$$= (rdt + \sigma\sqrt{dt} - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 dt) \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} S_t. \quad (1.11)$$

We will plug in (1.9) and (1.10) in (1.6) and cancel terms to produce

$$V(1 + rdt) = rS_t \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} dt + V + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S_t^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} dt + \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} dt$$

$$\text{or, } rdt = rS_t \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} dt + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S_t^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} dt + \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} dt.$$

We cancel dt from this equation to obtain the Black Scholes PDE

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + rS \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} - rV = 0.$$

1.8 Parity of Put-Call

We will make a portfolio with one long Call option and one short Put option [65]:

$$V_{PF}(S, T) = V_{ECO}(S, T) - V_{EPO}(S, T)$$

So it becomes,

$$V_{PF}(S, T) = \max(S - K, 0) - \max(K - S, 0) = S - K.$$

From the solution of Black-Scholes PDE with the final condition, we have,

$$V_{PF}(S, t) = S - Ke^{r(T-t)}.$$

Therefore we can say,

$$V_{ECO}(S, t) - V_{EPO}(S, t) = S - Ke^{r(T-t)}.$$

This is called the parity of Call-Put. As we can see from above:

$$\text{Call} - \text{Put} = \text{Asset} - \text{Forward}.$$

1.9 Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis of the Option price with respect to some parameters known as Greeks [65]:

- **Delta:** Δ is defined as:

$$\Delta = \frac{\partial V}{\partial S}.$$

It is the measurement of the rate of change of the option price V with respect to the change in the underlying asset price S .

Delta hedging use this **Delta** because the risk-less portfolio is stable in accordance to:

$$\frac{Q_S}{Q_V} = -\frac{\partial V}{\partial S} = -\Delta.$$

where Q_V , Q_S are Options and Stocks numbers in the Portfolio.

Now *Delta* for European Call and Put options are:

$$\Delta_{EC} = \frac{\partial V^{EC}}{\partial S} = N(d_1).$$

and

$$\Delta_{EP} = \frac{\partial V^{EP}}{\partial S} = -N(-d_1).$$

We can observe that:

$$\Delta^{EC} \in (0, 1) \text{ and } \Delta^{EP} \in (-1, 0)$$

Evaluation of Delta for market data time series:

We can figure out the implied volatility $\sigma_{implied}(t)$ from the market data series for the option price $V_{real}(t)$ and the underlying asset price $S_{real}(t)$. We have to solve:

$$V_{real}(t) = V^{EC}(S_{real}(t), t; \sigma_{implied}(t)).$$

- **Gamma:** It is defined as:

$$\Gamma = \frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial S} = \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2}$$

It is the measurement of the change of **Delta** of the option price V with respect to the change in the asset price S :

$$\Gamma^{EC} = \Gamma^{EP} = \frac{\partial \Delta^{EC}}{\partial S} = N'(d_1) \frac{\partial d_1}{\partial S} = \frac{e^{-\frac{1}{2}d_1^2}}{\sigma \sqrt{2\pi(T-t)}S}.$$

- **Rho:**

It is the sensitivity with respect to the interest rate r :

$$\rho = \frac{\partial V}{\partial r}.$$

So it calculates the rate of change of the option price V with respect to the interest rate r .

- **Theta:**

It is defined as :

$$\Theta = \frac{\partial V}{\partial t}.$$

So it calculates the rate of change of the option price V with respect to the interest rate t .

- **Vega:**

Sensitivity with respect to the volatility σ :

$$\nu = \frac{\partial V}{\partial \sigma}.$$

So it calculates the rate of change of the option price V with respect to the volatility σ .

The Black-Scholes Equation is:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + rS \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} - rV = 0.$$

The Greek Model for the Black-Scholes Equation is :

$$\Theta + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} S^2 \Gamma + rS \Delta - rV = 0.$$

Black-Scholes equation is important in the world of financial mathematics. In this chapter, we have given a description of the fundamental parts of Black-Scholes Equation.

Chapter 2

Linear Black-Scholes equation's Analytic Solution

2.1 Introduction

Black Scholes Equation is prominent in the quantitative finance world for the estimation of the option price. We discuss at length of the analytical solution of the Linear Equation in this chapter. Our main focus is to transform the Linear Black Scholes Equation into a heat-diffusion equation ; Then we solve the heat equation analytically. After that, we substitute the variables to get the solution of Black-Scholes PDE.

2.2 Black Scholes Equation's Linear Model

The Black Scholes partial differential equation [10] is

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + rS \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} - rV = 0. \quad (2.1)$$

Here

- $V \equiv V(S, t)$ is the payoff function. It is the price of the option at a time t . It is a two variable function with the asset's price S and time t .
- $S(t)$ stock price which the underlying asset's price at time t . It is also non negative.
- t is the time . Here t is from 0 to T . (T is the expiration time.)

- r is the riskless interest rate.
- σ is the volatility.
- K is the strike price of an option.
- μ is the drift rate.

In the case of Linear Black-Scholes Equation, σ, r, μ [65] are constants.

We convert the linear Black-Scholes Equation to a heat equation. We need to have the initial and boundary conditions if we want to find the solution of Black-Scholes Equation. We are considering only the European Option Price.

European Option Price: In this Option price, the domain of time t is,

$$0 \leq t \leq T$$

The domain of Stock price S is,

$$0 < S < \infty$$

European Call Option: From [10, 65]:

$$V(S, T) = \max(S - K, 0) \quad \text{for } 0 < S < \infty$$

$$V(0, t) = 0 \quad \text{for } t \in [0, T]$$

$$V(S, t) = S - Ke^{-r(T-t)} \quad \text{for } S \rightarrow \infty$$

European Put Option: From [10, 65]:

$$V(S, T) = \max(K - S, 0) \quad \text{for } 0 < S < \infty$$

$$V(0, t) = Ke^{-r(T-t)} \quad \text{for } t \in [0, T]$$

$$V(S, t) = 0 \quad \text{for } S \rightarrow \infty$$

2.3 Analytical Solution

This Black Scholes Equation has similarities with the Heat Equation [22]. Because Black-Scholes Equation also has the first derivative of a function (*Option Price*) with respect to time and the second derivative of a function(*Option Price*) with respect to space variable.

This Equation is in the form of Backward Parabolic. The reason for this is, Second derivative has the opposite sign with respect to the Heat Equation form which is Parabolic.

Our goal is to change the variables. So that the Black-Scholes Equation reduces to the Heat Equation. Then solve the Heat Equation. Finally we change the variables back to get solution of the original Black-Scholes Equation.

At first

$$t = T - \frac{\tau}{\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2},$$
$$S = Ke^x.$$

And we set

$$V(S, t) = K\nu(x, \tau).$$

We choose t in such a way that the backward parabolic equation becomes forward parabolic equation. And the transformation of S is very well known Euler Equation transformation.

From [69], We rewrite the change of variables

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma^2}{2}(T - t)$$

and

$$x = \log\left(\frac{S}{K}\right).$$

We figure out the first derivatives using the chain rule,

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \tau} \cdot \frac{d\tau}{dt} = K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \tau} \cdot \frac{-\sigma^2}{2}.$$

and

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial S} = K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{dx}{dS} = K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{1}{S}.$$

Now the second derivative is

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial S} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial S} \right) \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial S} \left(K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \right) \\
&= K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{-1}{S^2} + K \frac{\partial}{\partial S} \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{S} \\
&= K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{-1}{S^2} + K \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \right) \cdot \frac{dx}{dS} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \\
&= K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{-1}{S^2} + K \frac{\partial^2 \nu}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{1}{S^2}.
\end{aligned}$$

The terminal Condition is

$$V(S, T) = \max(S - K, 0) = \max(Ke^x - K, 0),$$

but

$$V(S, t) = K\nu(x, \tau),$$

so

$$V(S, T) = K\nu(x, T - T) = K\nu(x, 0).$$

Hence we get

$$\nu(x, 0) = \max(e^x - 1, 0).$$

We substitute all these derivatives into the Black-Scholes equation to get,

$$K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \tau} \cdot \frac{-\sigma^2}{2} + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} S^2 \left(K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{-1}{S^2} + K \frac{\partial^2 \nu}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{1}{S^2} \right) + rS \left(K \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \right) - rK\nu = 0.$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \tau} \cdot \frac{-\sigma^2}{2} + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} S^2 \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{-1}{S^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \nu}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{1}{S^2} \right) + rS \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \right) - r\nu = 0.$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{\sigma^2}{2} S^2 \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{-1}{S^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \nu}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{1}{S^2} \right) + rS \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \right) - r\nu = \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \tau} \cdot \frac{-\sigma^2}{2}$$

$$\text{or, } S^2 \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{-1}{S^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \nu}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{1}{S^2} \right) + rS \frac{1}{\sigma^2/2} \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \right) - r\nu \frac{1}{\sigma^2/2} = \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \tau}$$

$$\text{or, } S^2 \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{-1}{S^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \nu}{\partial x^2} \cdot \frac{1}{S^2} \right) + kS \left(\frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \right) - k\nu = \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \tau} \quad \text{where } k = \frac{r}{\sigma^2/2}$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial^2 \nu}{\partial x^2} + (k - 1) \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial x} - k\nu.$$

Therefore, we have a parameter k which does not have any dimension, it measures the risk-less interest rate as a multiple of volatility.

We have reconstructed time to expiry $\frac{\sigma^2}{2}.T$.

The equation is defined on the infinite interval on the spatial domain. $(-\infty < x < \infty)$.

We again simplify by changing the dependent variable,

$$\nu = e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u(x, \tau).$$

where α and β are constants. Now

$$\nu_\tau = \beta e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u + e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_\tau,$$

and

$$\nu_x = \alpha e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u + e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_x,$$

and

$$\nu_{xx} = \alpha^2 e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u + 2\alpha e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_x + e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau} u_{xx}.$$

We substitute these values into the equation and divide it by $e^{\alpha x + \beta \tau}$ get

$$\beta u + u_\tau = \alpha^2 u + 2\alpha u_x + u_{xx} + (k-1)(\alpha u + u_x) - ku.$$

from this we get

$$u_\tau = u_{xx} + [2\alpha + (k-1)]u_x + [\alpha^2 + (k-1)\alpha - k - \beta]u.$$

Now we choose

$$\alpha = -\frac{k-1}{2},$$

and

$$\beta = \alpha^2 + (k-1)\alpha - k = -\frac{(k+1)^2}{4}.$$

we substitute the values of α and β in the last equation to get:

$$u_\tau = u_{xx}.$$

This is the well known heat equation form

We need to convert the initial condition too.

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, 0) &= e^{-(-\frac{k-1}{2})x-0} \nu(x, 0) \\ &= e^{-(-\frac{k-1}{2})x} \max(e^x - 1, 0) \\ &= \max(e^{-\frac{k+1}{2}x} - e^{-\frac{k-1}{2}x}, 0). \end{aligned}$$

We have a function which is strictly positive, that is $u_0(x) > 0$ when $x > 0$, else $u_0(x) = 0$ when $x \leq 0$.

We are going to use Separation of Variables [34] to solve the **Heat-Equation**:

We have to change the variables for this particular integration.

$$\begin{aligned} z &= \frac{(s-x)}{\sqrt{2\pi}}. \\ dz &= -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} dx. \end{aligned}$$

hence the integration becomes:

$$u(x, \tau) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u_0(z\sqrt{2\tau} + x) e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz.$$

we are going to integrate over the domain where $u_0 > 0$.

In this domain,

$$u_0 = e^{\frac{k+1}{2} \cdot (x+z\sqrt{2\tau})} - e^{\frac{k-1}{2} \cdot (x+z\sqrt{2\tau})}.$$

The integration becomes:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-x/\sqrt{2\tau}}^{\infty} e^{\frac{k+1}{2}(x+z\sqrt{2\tau})} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-x/\sqrt{2\tau}}^{\infty} e^{\frac{k-1}{2}(x+z\sqrt{2\tau})} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz.$$

Let's set these integrals as:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-x/\sqrt{2\tau}}^{\infty} e^{\frac{k+1}{2}(x+z\sqrt{2\tau})} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz. \\ I_2 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-x/\sqrt{2\tau}}^{\infty} e^{\frac{k-1}{2}(x+z\sqrt{2\tau})} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz. \end{aligned}$$

We analyze I_1 first. The exponent part is:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{k+1}{2}(x+z\sqrt{2\tau}) - \frac{z^2}{2} \\
&= \left(\frac{-1}{2}\right)(z^2 - \sqrt{2\tau}(k+1)z) + \left(\frac{k+1}{2}\right)x \\
&= \left(\frac{-1}{2}\right)(z^2 - \sqrt{2\tau}(k+1)z + \tau\frac{(k+1)^2}{2}) + \left(\frac{k+1}{2}\right)x + \tau\frac{(k+1)^2}{4} \\
&= \left(\frac{-1}{2}\right)(z - \sqrt{\tau/2}(k+1))^2 + \left(\frac{k+1}{2}\right)x + \tau\frac{(k+1)^2}{4}.
\end{aligned}$$

Then we get

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-x/\sqrt{2\tau}}^{\infty} e^{\frac{k+1}{2}(x+z\sqrt{2\tau})} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz = \frac{e^{\left(\frac{k+1}{2}\right)x + \tau\frac{(k+1)^2}{4}}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-x/\sqrt{2\tau}}^{\infty} e^{\frac{-1}{2}(z - \sqrt{\tau/2}(k+1))^2} dz.$$

Again, We change the variables,

$$y = z - \sqrt{\tau/2}(k+1).$$

$$dy = dz.$$

Therefore, changing the limits of the Integration,

$$\frac{e^{\left(\frac{k+1}{2}\right)x + \tau\frac{(k+1)^2}{4}}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-x/\sqrt{2\tau} - \sqrt{\tau/2}(k+1)}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} dz.$$

We can represent this integral in terms of cumulative distribution function of a normal random variable denoted by Φ which is

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^d e^{-\frac{y^2}{2}} dy.$$

We get

$$I_1 = e^{\frac{(k+1)x}{2} + \tau\frac{(k+1)^2}{4}} \Phi(d_1).$$

where $d_1 = \frac{x}{\sqrt{2\tau}} + \sqrt{\frac{\tau}{2}}(k+1)$. The computation for I_2 is similar.

The Result of the Heat Equation is :

$$u(x, \tau) = e^{\frac{(k+1)x}{2} + \tau\frac{(k+1)^2}{4}} \Phi(d_1) - e^{\frac{(k-1)x}{2} + \tau\frac{(k-1)^2}{4}} \Phi(d_2).$$

where

$$d_1 = \frac{x}{\sqrt{2\tau}} + \sqrt{\frac{\tau}{2}}(k+1).$$

$$d_2 = \frac{x}{\sqrt{2\tau}} + \sqrt{\frac{\tau}{2}}(k-1).$$

Now, we substitute the variables to get the Black-Scholes equation.

$$\nu(x, \tau) = e^{-\frac{(k-1)x}{2} + \tau \frac{(k+1)^2}{4}} \cdot u(x, \tau).$$

The exponential terms neatly combine and cancel themselves. Going back to the starting of our analytical solution, the change of variables are,

$$x = \log(S/K),$$

$$\tau = \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2(T-t),$$

and

$$V(S, t) = K\nu(x, \tau).$$

The Black-Scholes formula is,

$$V(S, t) = S\Phi\left(\frac{\log(S/K) + (r + \sigma^2/2)(T-t)}{\sigma\sqrt{T-t}}\right) - Ke^{-r(T-t)}\Phi\left(\frac{\log(S/K) + (r - \sigma^2/2)(T-t)}{\sigma\sqrt{T-t}}\right).$$

We simplify this as:

$$d_1 = \frac{\log(S/K) + (r + \sigma^2/2)(T-t)}{\sigma\sqrt{T-t}}.$$

$$d_2 = \frac{\log(S/K) + (r - \sigma^2/2)(T-t)}{\sigma\sqrt{T-t}}.$$

We evaluate the value of call option,

$$V_C(S, t) = S \cdot \Phi(d_1) - Ke^{-r(T-t)} \cdot \Phi(d_2).$$

2.4 Graphical Solution of the Black-Scholes Equation

Let the strike price be $K = 100$. The risk-free interest rate is r is $.12$. The time of expiration is $T = 1$. The volatility is $\sigma = .10$. The value of the European Call

Option at expiry time plotted over a range of stock prices are $70 \leq S \leq 130$. We use the Black Scholes Equation's exact solution to evaluate the value of the option price before expiration.

Figure 2.1: Value of the European call option $V(S, t)$ at time, $t = 0, t = .2, t = .4, t = .6, t = .8$ and $t = 1$.

Figure 2.2: Value of the European call option $V(S, t)$ at various times in a surface plot

Black-Scholes Equation is effective for various contexts of the financial field. In this chapter, we investigated the analytical solution of the Linear Black-Scholes model. And a graphical representation of the exact solution is given too.

Chapter 3

Linear Black-Scholes Equation with Spectral Method

3.1 Introduction

We investigate Black-Scholes partial differential equation (PDE) with different Numerical schemes. In this chapter we solve it using spectral method. This method is well known for its superior efficiency and less time consumption. It takes less time than other numerical schemes such as finite-difference, finite elements and Gelarkin method. The spectral collocation method is applied for Black-Scholes PDE. We discuss briefly about the Spectral collocation method. There is a *MATLAB* execution of the Spectral Method [72]. We use the Chebyshev polynomial and Chebyshev points for the spectral method. Also there is a comparison of the numerical calculation with the exact solution at the end of this chapter.

3.2 Spectral Collocation Method

Spectral Method has the ability to achieve the exponential accuracy to solve the differential equations and approximating the solution [67]. The accuracy of the Spectral Method is ruled by the smoothness of functions.

We use polynomials to approximate a function [31]. The spectral collocation is also called pseudospectral method. Usually we use Chebyshev and Legendre polynomials. Let the weight be w_i and collocation point be x_i . These weights and collocation points connected to Chebyshev polynomial can be evaluated as [31]:

1. **Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto:** $x_i = \cos \frac{\pi i}{N}, w_0 = w_N = \frac{\pi}{2N}, w_i = \frac{\pi}{N}$
2. **Chebyshev-Gauss-Radau:** $x_i = \cos \frac{2\pi i}{2N+1}, w_0 = \frac{\pi}{2N+1}, w_i = \frac{2\pi}{2N+1}$
3. **Chebyshev-Gauss:** $x_i = \cos \frac{2i+1}{2N+2}, w_i = \frac{\pi}{N+1}$

3.3 Chebyshev Differentiation Matrix

We use the *Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto* points.

$$x_j = \cos \frac{\pi j}{N}, \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$$

And Chebyshev collocation points are evaluated in the interval $[-1, 1]$

We use these points to build up the Chebyshev Differentiation Matrix. And this matrix is used as the **differential** operator.

Now we are given a grid function v defined on the Chebyshev points; we acquire the discrete derivative g in two stages [72]:

- We let q be the unique polynomial with a degree $\leq M$ with $q(x_j) = v_j, 0 \leq j \leq M$
- $g_j = q'(x_j)$

Therefore this operation has to be linear. We can represent this by the multiplication of $(M + 1) \times (M + 1)$ matrix [72], which is denoted by D_M :

$$g = D_M v. \tag{3.1}$$

In here M is an arbitrary positive integer.

Now for $M = 1$. The interpolating points are:

$$x_0 = 1,$$

and

$$x_1 = -1.$$

The Lagrange form for the interpolating polynomial throughout the v_0 and v_1 is,

$$q(x) = \frac{1}{2}(1+x)v_0 + \frac{1}{2}(1-x)v_1.$$

The derivative of $q(x)$ is:

$$q'(x) = \frac{1}{2}v_0 - \frac{1}{2}v_1. \quad (3.2)$$

Here $M = 1$, so the matrix is 2×2 matrix.

Let's denote $a_{ij} = [a_{ij}]$ The entries of the matrix where $i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M$.

For the first column of the matrix, we set $x_0 = 1$ and get:

$$a_{11} = \frac{1}{2},$$

and

$$a_{21} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

For the second column of the matrix, we set $x_1 = -1$ and get:

$$a_{12} = -\frac{1}{2},$$

and

$$a_{22} = -\frac{1}{2}.$$

Hence the Chebyshev Differentiation Matrix for $M = 1$ is:

$$D_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Now for $M = 2$. The interpolating points are:

$$x_0 = 1, x_1 = 0, \text{ and } x_2 = -1.$$

The Lagrange form for the interpolating polynomial throughout the v_0, v_1 and v_2 is:

$$q(x) = \frac{1}{2}x(1+x)v_0 + (1+x)(1-x)v_1 + \frac{1}{2}x(1-x)v_2.$$

The derivative of $q(x)$ is:

$$q'(x) = (x + \frac{1}{2})v_0 - 2xv_1 + (x - \frac{1}{2})v_2. \quad (3.3)$$

Here $M = 2$, so the matrix is 3×3 matrix. For the first column of the matrix, we set $x_0 = 1$ and get:

$$a_{11} = x + \frac{1}{2} = \frac{3}{2},$$

For $x_1 = 0$,

$$a_{21} = x + \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

For $x_2 = -1$,

$$a_{31} = x + \frac{1}{2} = -\frac{1}{2}.$$

For the Second column of the matrix, we set $x_0 = 1$ and get:

$$a_{12} = -2x = -2,$$

For $x_1 = 0$,

$$a_{22} = -2x = 0,$$

For $x_2 = -1$,

$$a_{32} = -2x = 2.$$

For the Third column of the matrix, we set $x_0 = 1$ and get:

$$a_{13} = x - \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2},$$

For $x_1 = 0$,

$$a_{23} = x - \frac{1}{2} = -\frac{1}{2},$$

For $x_2 = -1$,

$$a_{33} = x - \frac{1}{2} = -\frac{3}{2}.$$

Therefore the Chebyshev Differentiation Matrix for $M = 2$ is:

$$D_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{3}{2} & -2 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & 2 & -\frac{3}{2} \end{pmatrix}.$$

We can give the generalization for the entries of D_M for arbitrary M [72, 30]

Theorem: Let's consider for $M \geq 1$, we have the columns and rows $(M+1) \times (M+1)$ of the Chebyshev Spectral Differentiation Matrix D_M from 0 to M . The entries of this matrix are:

$$(D_M)_{00} = \frac{2M^2 + 1}{6}, \quad (D_M)_{MM} = -\frac{2M^2 + 1}{6}, \quad (3.4)$$

$$(D_M)_{jj} = \frac{-x_j}{2(1-x_j^2)}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, M-1. \quad (3.5)$$

$$(D_M)_{ij} = \frac{c_i}{c_j} \frac{(-1)^{i+j}}{(x_i - x_j)}, \quad , i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, M-1. \quad (3.6)$$

where

$$c_i = \begin{cases} 2 & i = 0 \text{ or } M \\ 1 & \text{elsewhere.} \end{cases}$$

We can write this in Matrix form,

$$D_M = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{2M^2+1}{6} & 2\frac{(-1)^j}{1-x_j} & \dots & \dots & 2\frac{(-1)^j}{1-x_j} & \frac{1}{2}(-1)^M \\ -\frac{1}{2}\frac{(-1)^i}{1-x_i} & \frac{-x_j}{2(1-x_j^2)} & \frac{(-1)^{i+j}}{(x_i-x_j)} & \dots & \frac{(-1)^{i+j}}{(x_i-x_j)} & \frac{1}{2}\frac{(-1)^{M+i}}{1+x_i} \\ \vdots & \frac{(-1)^{i+j}}{(x_i-x_j)} & \frac{-x_j}{2(1-x_j^2)} & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \frac{(-1)^{i+j}}{(x_i-x_j)} & \vdots \\ -\frac{1}{2}\frac{(-1)^i}{1-x_i} & \frac{(-1)^{i+j}}{(x_i-x_j)} & \dots & \frac{(-1)^{i+j}}{(x_i-x_j)} & \frac{-x_j}{2(1-x_j^2)} & \frac{1}{2}\frac{(-1)^{M+i}}{1+x_i} \\ -\frac{1}{2}(-1)^M & -2\frac{(-1)^{M+j}}{1+x_j} & \dots & \dots & -2\frac{(-1)^{M+j}}{1+x_j} & -\frac{2M^2+1}{6} \end{pmatrix}.$$

The j th column of D_M carries the derivative of the degree M polynomial interpolant $q_j(x)$ to the delta function bolstered at x_j , represented at the grid points x_i

If we have zero boundary conditions, then evaluation becomes easier. We can exclude the first and last column of D_M matrix because they will be multiplied by zero.

3.4 MATLAB function : 'cheb'

A **MATLAB** function called **cheb** [72] is used to evaluate the Chebyshev differentiation matrix D_M . This function returns a vector x and a matrix D . The function

is given below:

```
% CHEB Evaluate Diff = Chebyshev differentiation matrix, x = Chebyshev grid
function [Diff,x] = cheb(M)
if M==0, Diff=0; x=1; return, end
x = cos(pi*(0:M)/M)';
c1 = [2; ones(M-1,1); 2].*(-1).^(0:M)';
X = repmat(x,1,M+1);
dX = X-X';
Diff = (c1*(1./c1)')./(dX+(eye(M+1)));
Diff = Diff - diag(sum(Diff'));
```

This MATLAB function does not evaluate D_M precisely by the (3.4, 3.5, 3.6) formulas. Instead this makes the best use of (3.5) for the off-diagonal entries but then acquires the diagonal (3.4, 3.5) from the identity:

$$(D_M)_{ii} = - \sum_{\substack{j=0 \\ j \neq i}}^N (D_M)_{ij}.$$

From this, it is slightly easy to program. And it creates a matrix with better stability properties [59, 7].

We are giving a few **Chebyshev Differentiation Matrix** D_M matrices evaluated by the MATLAB function **cheb**:

```
>> cheb(1)
```

```
ans =
```

```
    0.5000    -0.5000
    0.5000    -0.5000
```

```
>> cheb(2)
```

```
ans =
```

```
1.5000 -2.0000 0.5000
0.5000 0 -0.5000
-0.5000 2.0000 -1.5000
```

```
>> cheb(3)
```

```
ans =
```

```
3.1667 -4.0000 1.3333 -0.5000
1.0000 -0.3333 -1.0000 0.3333
-0.3333 1.0000 0.3333 -1.0000
0.5000 -1.3333 4.0000 -3.1667
```

```
>> cheb(4)
```

```
ans =
```

```
5.5000 -6.8284 2.0000 -1.1716 0.5000
1.7071 -0.7071 -1.4142 0.7071 -0.2929
-0.5000 1.4142 0 -1.4142 0.5000
0.2929 -0.7071 1.4142 0.7071 -1.7071
-0.5000 1.1716 -2.0000 6.8284 -5.5000
```

Here we can analyze that first two Matrices D_1 and D_2 matches with the entries of the matrices we evaluated analytically. Therefore this function **cheb** is accurate.

We evaluate **European Call Option** considering the following the parameters:

$$T = 1; \quad r = 0.1, \quad \sigma = 0.2; \quad K = 100. \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.1: European Call Option Price $V(S, t)$ using Spectral Collocation Method.

Then we have the comparison with the exact solution of **Black-Scholes** Equation. And it matches with the exact solution,

Figure 3.2: The comparison of European Call Option Price $V(S, t)$ with the Exact solution.

Now we have the table of errors compared to Spectral Collocation Method. We use infinity norm at $t = 0$.

Stock Price S	Spectral Collocation Method	Exact Value	Error
224.79080	134.29722	134.30707	0.00985
227.04998	136.55662	136.56625	0.00963
229.33187	138.83875	138.84814	0.00939
231.63670	141.14384	141.15296	0.00912
233.96469	143.47213	143.48095	0.00882
236.31607	145.82384	145.83233	0.00849
238.69109	148.19921	148.20735	0.00813
241.08997	150.59849	150.60623	0.00774
243.51297	153.02191	153.02923	0.00731
245.96031	155.46972	155.47657	0.00685
248.43225	157.94216	157.94851	0.00635
250.92904	160.43949	160.44530	0.00581
253.45092	162.96194	162.96718	0.00524
255.99814	165.50978	165.51440	0.00462
258.57097	168.08327	168.08722	0.00396
261.16965	170.68265	170.68591	0.00326
263.79445	173.30819	173.31070	0.00251

Table 3.1: Comparison of Spectral Method and Exact Solution for European Call option price $V(S, t)$ with respect to the parameters in (3.7).

3.6 Stability and Convergence of Spectral Method

- **Stability:**

Let's consider the equation:

$$u_t = S(x)u_{xx}, \quad -1 \leq x \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq t \leq S(x),$$

$$u(\pm 1, t) = 0.$$

Now, let u_N be the Chebyshev collocation approximation. Then the stability can be demonstrated as [6]:

$$\sum_{j=0}^N \frac{u_N^2(x_j, t)}{S(x_j)} w_j \leq \sum_{j=0}^N \frac{u_N^2(x_j, 0)}{S(x_j)} w_j.$$

Our Transformed Heat equation from Black-Schole PDE is of the form:

$$u_\tau = u_{xx}.$$

Therefore in this case we have, $S(x) = 1$.

- **Convergence:**

We are considering that $I_N u$ is the interpolating polynomial and u is the approximation. The difference between u and $I_N u$ exponentially goes to 0 for consistent functions. Let C^m be a function of u . Upper bounds on the difference between u and $I_N u$ can be found for various norms and choice of polynomials. $\|u - I_N u\|$ can be evaluated for **Chebyshev** [31]:

$$\|u - I_N u\|_{L_w^2} \leq \frac{C}{N^m} \sum_{i=0}^m \|u^{(i)}\|_{L_w^2}.$$

$$\|u - I_N u\|_{L_\infty} \leq \frac{C}{N^{m-\frac{1}{2}}} \sum_{i=0}^m \|u^{(i)}\|_{L_w^2}.$$

By increasing the power of N , the error decreases. Therefore $|u - I_N u| \rightarrow 0$ as N increases. We can safely say that the approximation converges.

3.7 Conclusion

We have given the introduction of spectral collocation method in this chapter. In that method, we use Chebyshev grid points and polynomial. We also show the computational competence of Spectral Method through Black-Scholes Equations. This method has the ability of computing faster than most other numerical schemes.

Chapter 4

Differential Quadrature Method for Linear Black-Scholes Equation

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter , we discuss about Differential Quadrature Method (DQM) which is able to obtain highly accurate numerical solutions of differential equations by using a few grid points [63]. A Differential Quadrature method which is proposed here can be used to solve boundary-value and initial-value differential equations with a linear or nonlinear nature. Unlike the classic Differential Quadrature Method (DQM), the newly proposed Differential Quadrature Method chooses the function values and some derivatives wherever necessary as independent variables [78]. This very method is known for its simplicity and efficiency [53]. We briefly discuss about the Differential Quadrature Method. Then we incorporate this method into **Black-Scholes** PDE. This method is analogous with the Spectral Collocation method or Pseudospectral Method [75]. Principally, spatial discretization is completed using Differential Quadrature Method. Then derivatives of a function at discretized points are computed using this method. Then there is a comparison between our solved Black-Scholes Equation using Differential Quadrature Method with the exact solution.

4.2 Differential Quadrature Method (DQM)

Differential Quadrature Method is used to solve initial value problem and boundary value problem [78]. In this method, the weighting coefficients are needed. To find the

weighting coefficients, we use an approximating function [75]. There are various ways to compute the approximating functions. A conventional method of approximating function is called Polynomial Differential Quadrature Method (PDQM) [45]. Here N th degree of Lagrange Polynomial is used. As we have used the **Heat Equation** in the Spectral Method chapter, we repeat this in this chapter too. Because we are not going to solve the Classical **Black-Scholes** Equation but going to solve the converted Heat Equation:

$$u_\tau = u_{xx}.$$

From this we get solutions in the form of $u(x, \tau)$ where x refers to the spatial domain and τ is time domain. And the function evaluates temperature at time τ . The approximated solution $u(x, \tau)$ can be written as:

$$u(x_i, \tau) = \sum_{k=1}^N A_{ik} u(x_k, \tau).$$

Where A_{ik} represents the weighting function at the grid point x_i , $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$. Therefore the grid points are $x_1 < x_2 < x_3 < \dots < x_N$ which means $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N)$.

4.3 Discretization of domain and Stability

We have spatial domain which is discretized by Differential Quadrature Method (DQM) and explicit finite difference method (FDM) for the time domain. We use differential Quadrature Method (DQM) to discretize spatial derivatives. Mainly, we use the Polynomial Differential Quadrature Method (PDQM) [45]. We use Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto grid points for spatial discretization which has a stable outcome [66]. Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto grid points are:

$$x_i = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \cos \frac{(i-1)\pi}{N-1} \right), \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N.$$

In differential quadrature method (DQM), stability majorly depends on the eigenvalues of the differential quadrature discretization matrices. The very eigenvalues depend on how the grid points are distributed. From [66], uniform grid points such as $x_i = x_1 + ih$, $i = 2, 3, \dots, N$, usually do not give stable solution whereas

Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto give better accuracy and stable solution. For the temporal domain, we use explicit finite difference method (FDM) [53]. The finite difference method (FDM) of explicit kind is known for its simplicity and it provides accurate results if we input proper choice of time steps. In the solution using explicit finite difference method (FDM); it solves the linear system of equations iteratively from one time grid to another.

4.4 Derivatives of Space by using Differential Quadrature Method

In this part, we use Differential Quadrature Method (DQM) to make approximation of spatial derivatives. The differential quadrature method (DQM) is used for the discretization of the first and the second derivatives at a grid point x_i is given below [45]:

$$u_x(x_i, \tau) = \sum_{k=1}^N A_{ik}^{(1)} u(x_k, \tau).$$

$$u_{xx}(x_i, \tau) = \sum_{k=1}^N A_{ik}^{(2)} u(x_k, \tau).$$

Generalizing,

$$u_l(x_i, \tau) = \sum_{k=1}^N A_{ik}^{(l)} u(x_k, \tau).$$

where $A_{ik}^{(1)}, A_{ik}^{(2)}, A_{ik}^{(l)}$ are the weighting coefficients, $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$.

Here we make the usage of Lagrange's polynomial for the weighting coefficients [45].

We can obtain the weighting coefficients from the base functions:

$$p_k(x) = \frac{M(x)}{(x - x_k)M^{(1)}(x_k)}, \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N.$$

where

$$M(x) = (x - x_1)(x - x_2) \cdots (x - x_N),$$

$$M^{(1)}(x_i) = \prod_{k=1, k \neq i}^N (x_i - x_k).$$

We can express these in the **Matrix** formation.

1. **The first order derivative:** From [45, 53], we can express diagonal and off diagonal entries of the weighting coefficients of the first order.

Diagonal entry: $i = j$,

$$A_{ij}^{(1)} = \sum_{k=1, k \neq i}^N \frac{1}{(x_i - x_k)} = - \sum_{k=1, k \neq i}^N A_{ik}^{(1)}.$$

Off-diagonal entry: $i \neq j$,

$$\begin{aligned} A_{ij}^{(1)} &= \frac{\prod_{k=1, k \neq i}^N (x_i - x_k)}{(x_j - x_i) \prod_{k=1, k \neq j}^N (x_j - x_k)} \\ &= \frac{1}{(x_j - x_i)} \frac{\prod_{k=1, k \neq i}^N (x_i - x_k)}{\prod_{k=1, k \neq j}^N (x_j - x_k)} \\ &= \frac{1}{(x_j - x_i)} \cdot \prod_{k=1, k \neq i, k \neq j}^N \frac{(x_i - x_k)}{(x_j - x_k)}. \end{aligned}$$

2. **Second order Derivative**

Diagonal entry: $i = j$,

$$A_{ij}^{(2)} = - \sum_{k=1, k \neq i}^N A_{ik}^{(2)}.$$

Off-diagonal entry: $i \neq j$,

$$A_{ij}^{(2)} = 2A_{ij}^{(1)} \left(A_{ii}^{(1)} - \frac{1}{x_i - x_j} \right).$$

3. **Higher Order Derivatives:** As we can see from the first two cases, there is a recurrence formula for the higher derivatives. That is, to evaluate weighting coefficients of higher order, we need the weighting coefficients of all the lower orders relative to the one we need.

Diagonal entry: $i = j$,

$$A_{ij}^{(l)} = - \sum_{k=1, k \neq i}^N A_{ik}^{(l)}.$$

Off-diagonal entry: $i \neq j$,

$$A_{ij}^{(l)} = l \left(A_{ij}^{(1)} A_{ii}^{(l-1)} - \frac{A_{ij}^{(l-1)}}{(x_i - x_j)} \right).$$

We have a **Heat Equation** to solve. We replace the second derivative in it by the **Differential Quadrature Matrix**.

$$D_{QM} = [A_{ij}].$$

$$u_{xx} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = D_{QM}^2 u.$$

4.5 Matlab function : Differential Quadrature Matrix

Mehmet Murat Altug Bicak coded the matlab function file for Differential Quadrature Matrix [9]. The function file is given below:

```
function [D]=Diff_Quad(N)
% Differential quadrature matrix for N points based on Lobatto grid points.
for ii=1:N
X(ii)=0.5*(1-cos((ii-1)*pi/(N-1)));
end
SagTaraf=1;
Taraf=0;
for ii=1:N
for jj=1:N
if ii~=jj
a1=(1/(X(jj)-X(ii)));
for k=1:N
if k~=ii & k~=jj
SagTaraf=SagTaraf*(X(ii)-X(k))/(X(jj)-X(k));
end
end
end
```

```

a(ii,jj)=a1*SagTaraf;
SagTaraf=1;
end

if ii==jj
    for k=1:N
        if k~=ii
            Taraf=Taraf+(1/(X(ii)-X(k)));
        end
    end
end

a(ii,jj)=Taraf;
Taraf=0;
end
end

end
D=a;
tic

```

A few outputs of **Differential Quadrature Matrix** produced by the function file are given below:

```

>> Diff_Quad(1)
ans =
    0

>> Diff_Quad(2)
ans =
    -1     1
    -1     1

>> Diff_Quad(3)
ans =
   -3.0000    4.0000   -1.0000

```

```

-1.0000    0.0000    1.0000
 1.0000   -4.0000    3.0000
>> Diff_Quad(4)
ans =
-6.3333    8.0000   -2.6667    1.0000
-2.0000    0.6667    2.0000   -0.6667
 0.6667   -2.0000   -0.6667    2.0000
-1.0000    2.6667   -8.0000    6.333

```

4.6 Numerically solving Black-Scholes PDE using Differential Quadrature Method

Here, we use Differential Quadrature Method (DQM) to solve the transformed Equation (*Heat equation*) of Black-Scholes PDE.

We evaluate the Differential Quadrature Matrix (DQM) with the help of [9] for Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto Grid points. This differential quadrature matrix converts the differential equation into a eigenvalue problem($y' = A * y \implies Dy = Ay$).

We solve the Black-Scholes Equation for the domain $x \in [-1, 1]$. Now for our choice of Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto points, we get the grid points in the interval $[0, 1]$. To convert the interval from $[0, 1]$ to $[-1, 1]$, we use $2x - 1$.

We evaluate **European Call Option** $V(S, t)$ for the following parameters:

$$T = 1; \quad r = 0.02, \quad \sigma = 0.2; \quad K = 100.$$

Figure 4.1: European Call Option Price $V(S, t)$ using Differential Quadrature Method.

Then we have the comparison with the exact solution of **Black-Scholes** Equation. And it matches with the exact solution:

Figure 4.2: European Call Option Price $V(S, t)$ is compared with the Exact solution.

Now we have the table of errors compared to Differential Quadrature Method. We use infinity norm at $t = 0$.

Stock Price S	Differential Quadrature Method	Exact Value	Error
137.71278	47.37890	47.37287	0.00603
139.09681	48.74329	48.73885	0.00444
141.90675	50.12376	50.12078	0.00298
143.33294	52.93267	52.93226	0.00042
144.77346	54.36104	54.36175	0.00070
146.22846	55.80532	55.80704	0.00173
147.69808	57.26551	57.26816	0.00265
149.18247	58.74161	58.74510	0.00349
150.68178	60.23366	60.23791	0.00426
152.19616	61.74168	61.74663	0.00494
153.72575	63.26574	63.27130	0.00557
155.27072	64.80588	64.81200	0.00613
156.83122	66.36218	66.36881	0.00663

Table 4.1: Comparison of Differential Quadrature Method and Exact Solution for the European Call Option Price $V(S, t)$.

4.7 Conclusion

Introduction to Differential Quadrature Method is given in this chapter. We built up the differential quadrature matrix which helped extensively in our MATLAB implementation of Black-Scholes PDE.

Chapter 5

Nonlinear Black Scholes Equation and Volatility Models

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter we discuss about Nonlinear Black Scholes Equation and several volatility models. A short and efficient analytical approach for the Nonlinear Black Scholes Equation is given too. We focus on the European Option price.

5.2 Nonlinear Black Scholes Equation

The linear Black Scholes Equation is:

$$V_t + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 V_{SS} + rSV_S - rV = 0. \quad (5.1)$$

Here $S(t) > 0$ and $t \in (0, T)$ There are some restrictive assumptions on the linear Black-Scholes Equation which do not match in reality. Because of transaction costs,[5, 11, 51],large investor preferences [27, 29, 64] and and incomplete markets[68]. In this thesis, we focus on couple of transaction cost models for the nonlinear Black–Scholes equations for European option price where μ the drift rate is constant and modified volatility function is not constant,

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \tilde{\sigma}^2(t, S, V_S, V_{SS}).$$

So the equation (5.1) becomes *the nonlinear Black Scholes Equation*:

$$V_t + \frac{1}{2}\tilde{\sigma}^2(t, S, V_S, V_{SS})S^2V_{SS} + rSV_S - rV = 0 \quad (5.2)$$

where $S(t) > 0$ and $t \in (0, T)$.

5.3 Boundary Conditions

We have to finalize the differential problem by stating the terminal and boundary conditions for European Call and European Put Option price. Only then we can find a unique solution for the equation (5.2).

Although we only focus on European Call Option Price in this dissertation.

5.3.1 European Call Option

European call option is the solution of (5.2) on $0 \leq S < \infty$, $0 \leq t \leq T$ with the following initial condition and boundary conditions:

$$V(S, T) = (S - K)^+, \text{ for } 0 \leq S < \infty,$$

$$V(0, t) = 0,$$

$$V(S, t) \approx S - Ke^{-r(T-t)}, \text{ as } S \rightarrow \infty.$$

5.3.2 European Put Option

The value $V(S, t)$ of the European put option is the solution of **1.2** on $0 \leq S < \infty$, $0 \leq t \leq T$ with the following initial condition and boundary conditions:

$$V(S, T) = (K - S)^+, \text{ for } 0 \leq S < \infty,$$

$$V(0, t) = Ke^{-r(T-t)},$$

$$V(S, t) \approx 0, \text{ as } S \rightarrow \infty.$$

5.4 Volatility Models

In classical Black-Scholes model, the essential parameter which can not be observed but is assumed to be constant is known as the volatility σ . Many researchers tried different approaches to improve the model by using a modified volatility function $\tilde{\sigma}(\cdot)$ to take transaction costs into account, big traders and illiquid markets which is eventually the cause of the nonlinearity of (5.2). In this part, we discuss briefly about couple of volatility models and focus will be on the transaction cost related volatility models.

1. We can replace the volatility σ in the Black-Scholes model by the approximated volatility from the preceding values of the underlying asset. This volatility is called the historical volatility [32].
2. We can calculate the modified volatility from the exact solution of the Classical Black-Scholes Model if the price of Option and every other parameters are known. The implied volatility is the value σ , for which call option solution and put option solution is true in comparison to the real market data. We can evaluate the implied volatility from the difference between the observed option price $V(S, t)$ (from stock market) and the Black-Scholes exact solution where all the parameters are taken into account from the reality except for the implied volatility.
3. Another model is developed by Hull,White[38] and Heston[35], volatility follows the dynamics of a stochastic process which is called the stochastic volatility.
4. At first we have observed volatilities at each stock price and time which is termed as local volatility $\tilde{\sigma} = \tilde{\sigma}(S, t)$. We can replace constant volatilities with them. Dupire [50] investigated the reliances and expressed the local volatility as a function of implicit volatilities.
5. We assume that every security is accessible at any size and any time or that any single trading will not impact the price, is not always correct. Hence,several authors have modeled illiquid markets and big trader effects.Frey and Stremme [23]and after some time Frey and Patie [28] examined these results on the price and emerge with the outcome

$$\tilde{\sigma} = \frac{\sigma}{1 - \rho\lambda(S)SV_{SS}}. \quad (5.3)$$

where ρ is constant, σ the historical volatility.

These nonlinear models are all consistent with the linear model if the supplementary parameters for transaction cost vanish ($Le, \Psi(\cdot), M$).

There are couple of modified volatility function models,

5.5 Leland's Model for Volatility

Leland's model is one of the infamous implied volatility model. By the trade at discrete times [51] was the plan of Leland's to relax the hedging conditions. This also has the potential to reduce the Portfolio adjustment expenses. Leland assumes that the transaction cost is

$$\omega |\Delta| S/2.$$

where ω is the whole trip transaction cost per unit money of the transaction. Δ is the number of assets purchased ($\Delta > 0$) or sold ($\Delta < 0$) at price S , is proportional to the monetary value of the assets purchased or sold.

We take a portfolio which replicates with Δ units of the underlying asset and the bond B :

$$\Pi = \Delta S + B.$$

After that, a minor change in time of the size δt the change in the portfolio becomes

$$\delta\Pi = \Delta\delta S + rB\delta t - \frac{\omega}{2} |\delta\Delta| S. \quad (5.4)$$

Here δS is the change in price S . Therefore, the first term represents the change in value. Then we have the 2nd which represents the bond growth in δt time. After that we have $\delta\Delta$ which represents the change in the number of assets. Hence, the last term becomes the transaction cost because of the portfolio change.

We use Ito's lemma for the value of the option price $V := V(S, t)$ and get:

$$\delta V = V_S\delta S + (V_t + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} S^2 V_{SS})\delta t. \quad (5.5)$$

We assume that the option V is replicated by the portfolio Π and their values have to be equivalent at all times and there can be no risk-less profit. Because of no-arbitrage argument, we get

$$\delta\Pi = \delta V$$

Equating the terms in the last two equations, we get

$$\Delta = V_S,$$

$$rB\delta t - \frac{\omega}{2} |\delta\Delta| S = (V_t + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} S^2 V_{SS}) \delta t.$$

Leland showed in his paper that:

$$\frac{\omega}{2} |\delta\Delta| S = \frac{\sigma^2}{2} Le \cdot S^2 |V_{SS}| \delta t.$$

Here Le is the *leland number*, which is:

$$Le = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \cdot \frac{\omega}{\sigma \sqrt{\delta t}}.$$

where δt is the transaction frequency. And ω is the round trip transaction cost per unit money of the transaction. From the previous equations, we can say that:

$$B = \Pi - \Delta S = V - SV_S.$$

Hence

$$rV - rSV_S - \frac{\sigma^2}{2} Le S^2 |V_{SS}| = V_t + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} S^2 V_{SS}.$$

As a result, Leland concludes that the option price is the solution of the non-linear Black-Scholes equation:

$$V_t + \frac{\tilde{\sigma}^2}{2} S^2 V_{SS} + rSV_S - rV = 0.$$

In this model the modified volatility is:

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2 (1 + Le \cdot \text{sign}(V_{SS})).$$

Here

$$\text{sign}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } x < 0. \end{cases}$$

Here σ represents the historical volatility and Le the Leland number. The Leland Number is defined in such a way that the more repeated the rebalancing (δt smaller), the transaction costs get higher which makes a bigger value of V .

We know that $V_{SS} > 0$ for European Puts and Calls when transaction cost is absent. We assume that it behaves in the same way when there is transaction cost present, equation linear with an adjusted constant volatility $\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2 (1 + Le) > \sigma^2$.

This model has played a major role in the quantitative finance field. Even though it was denounced by Kabanov and Safarian in [48]. They showed that there is a hedging error in Leland's Model. The limitation of his model is the convexity of the resulting option price V (So, $V_{SS} > 0$). And this model considers only one option in the portfolio. Avellaneda and Paras extended this model [4].

5.6 Boyle and Vorst Volatility Model

Boyle and Vorst derived [12] the binomial model with discrete trading procedures (with the help of central limit theorem) and transaction costs. When the transaction cost ω and the time step δt tend to zero, the option price converges to a Black-Scholes model price with the modified volatility of the form

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + Le\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}\text{sign}(V_{SS})).$$

As Leland, assumed convexity of V . Boyle and Vorst also did the same assumption. So that the $\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + Le\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}})$ and the Black-Scholes PDE converts into a linear equation.

5.7 Paras and Avellaneda Volatility Model

Paras and Avellaneda derived the exact same volatility as Leland using the binomial model and the algorithm of Bensaid [8]. When $V_{SS} \leq 0$ and $Le \geq 1$, the nonlinear Black-Scholes PDE results in a mathematically ill posed and does not have solution. For the other case $V_{SS} > 0$ and $Le \geq 1$ they suggested couple of hedging schemes.

5.8 Hodges and Neuberger Volatility Model

Neuberger and Hodges proposed a completely separate approach to model transaction costs [36]. They considered a function called utility function without any specification and assuming that the performance of the shareholder is identified by this function. This utility function estimates the corresponding contentment of the shareholder from the input. They showed that the Black-Scholes Option price is the deviation between

the greatest utility from the terminal capital with and without option liability. They hypothesized that the Option price in a stock market having the transaction costs should be equal to the distinctive money gain which balances out this deviation. Davis, Panas and Zariphopoulou [21] advanced this theory when the transaction cost is present. There was modification made by Constantinides and Zariphopoulou [16] to attain universal bounds independent of the utility function.

5.9 Barles' and Soner Model

Barles and Soner developed [5] a supplemental complex model from the utility function scheme of Neuberger and Hodges [36].

We will take into account of a procedure where possession of bonds is denoted by $X(s)$ and the procedure of the shares possessed is denoted by $Y(s)$. We have a scheme for trading $(L(s), M(s))$ which are a pair increasing processes having the property $L(t) = M(t) = 0$. These are clarified as the cumulative transfers. These transfers are measured in the shares of stock. $M(s)$ is evaluated in shares from stock to bond and $L(s)$ is calculated in shares from bond to stock . Then we select $\omega \in (0, 1)$ be the proportional transaction cost.

The procedures $X(s)$ and $Y(s)$ begin with the initial values x and y , $s \in [t, T]$ and develop in accordance with

$$X(s) = x - \int_t^s S(\tau)(1 + \omega)dL(\tau) + \int_t^s S(\tau)(1 - \omega)dM(\tau) \quad (5.6)$$

and

$$Y(s) = y + L(s) - M(s). \quad (5.7)$$

The buying of shares of stock at a price surges up by the proportional transaction is exhibited by the first integral of (4.6). The selling of stock at a decreased price of the transaction cost is exhibited by the second integral . We include the amount of stocks bought and withdraw the amount of stocks sold to the initial capital of stocks possessed in the second equation.

Neuberger and Hodges [36] declares that in the utility maximization that European Call Option price can be acquired by the deviation of having no option liability and

when the liability is present. Subsequently, Barles and Soner approach consider two maximiation problems. Let's consider the exponential *utility function* be ,

$$U(\xi) = 1 - e^{\gamma\xi}.$$

Here $\gamma > 0$ is the risk aversion factor. The first value function is the expected utility from the final capital without any option liabilities taken over the transfer processes

$$V_1(x, y, S(t), t) = \sup_{L(\cdot), M(\cdot)} E[U(X(T) + Y(T)S(T))].$$

Then we have another value function which is the expected utility from the final capital. We assume that , we have sold N European call options taken over the transfer processes,

$$V_2(x, y, S(t), t) = \sup_{L(\cdot), M(\cdot)} E[U(X(T) + Y(T)S(T) - N(S(T) - K)^+)].$$

The price of every option is equal to the maximal solution Λ of the algebraic equation is proposed by Hodges and Neuberger.

$$\begin{aligned} V_2(x + N\Lambda, y, S(t), t) &= \sup_{L(\cdot), M(\cdot)} E[U(X(T) + N\Lambda + Y(T)S(T) - N(S(T) - K)^+)] \\ &= \sup_{L(\cdot), M(\cdot)} E[U(X(T) + Y(T)S(T) - N(S(T) - K)^+)] \\ &= V_1(x, y, S(t), t). \end{aligned}$$

So from this we conclude that the option price Λ is equivalent to the inclusion of the initial capital at time t which was required to deal with liabilities of option appearing at T . We have the right to state that the argument of linearity that by selling N Options with the risk aversion factor γ gives the identical price as selling one option with risk aversion factor γN . This leads the way to executing an asymptotic analysis as $\gamma N \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, we can say that

$$U(\xi) = 1 - e^{\gamma N \xi}$$

and

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{\gamma N}.$$

so

$$U_\epsilon(\xi) = 1 - e^{-\frac{\xi}{\epsilon}}, \quad \xi \in \mathbb{R}.$$

The optimization problem becomes

$$V_1(x, y, S(t), t) = 1 - \inf_{L(\cdot), M(\cdot)} E[e^{-\frac{1}{\epsilon}(X(T)+Y(T)S(T))}]$$

and

$$V_2(x, y, S(t), t) = 1 - \inf_{L(\cdot), M(\cdot)} E[e^{-\frac{1}{\epsilon}(X(T)+Y(T)S(T)-(S(T)-K)^+)}].$$

Barles and Soner define $z_{1,2} : \mathbb{R} \times (0, \infty) \times (0, T) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by

$$V_1(x, y, S(t), t) = 1 - \inf_{L(\cdot), M(\cdot)} E[e^{-\frac{1}{\epsilon}(x+yS(t)-z_1(y, S(t), t))}]$$

and

$$V_2(x, y, S(t), t) = 1 - \inf_{L(\cdot), M(\cdot)} E[e^{-\frac{1}{\epsilon}(x+yS(t)-z_2(y, S(t), t))}].$$

so ,

$$z_1(y, S(t), T) = 0$$

and

$$z_2(y, S(t), T) = (S(T) - K)^+.$$

Therefore the Option price becomes,

$$\Lambda(x, y, S(t), t; \frac{1}{\epsilon}, 1) = z_2(y, S(t), t) - z_1(y, S(t), t).$$

Barles and Soner state from the theory of stochastic optimal control that the value functions V_1 and V_2 are the unique solutions of the dynamic programming equation

$$\min(-V_t + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S^2 V_{SS} - rSV_S, -V_y + S(1 + \kappa)V_x, V_y - S(1 - \kappa)V_x) = 0.$$

which eventually leads to a dynamic programming equation for the variable z_1 and z_2 which are independent of the variable x . Suppose that the proportional transaction cost,

$$\kappa = a\sqrt{\epsilon} \text{ for some } a > 0.$$

Now as $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ and $\kappa \rightarrow 0$.

$$z_1 \rightarrow 0$$

and

$$z_2 \rightarrow V.$$

Here V is the unique (viscosity) solution of the nonlinear Black-Scholes equation

$$V_t + \frac{1}{2}\tilde{\sigma}^2 S^2 V_{SS}^2 + rSV_S - rV = 0,$$

where

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + \Psi(e^{r(T-t)} a^2 S^2 V_{SS})).$$

Where σ denotes the historical volatility with $a = \frac{\kappa}{\sqrt{\epsilon}}$ and $\Psi(x)$ denotes the solution to the following nonlinear ordinary differential equation

$$\Psi'(x) = \frac{\Psi(x) + 1}{2\sqrt{x\Psi(x) - x}}, \quad x \neq 0.$$

with the initial condition

$$\Psi(0) = 0.$$

From analysis, we conclude that

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Psi(x)}{x} = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} \frac{\Psi(x)}{x} = -1.$$

This characteristic recommends to treat the function $\Psi(\cdot)$ as the identity for big arguments and therefore simplifying the calculations. In this case the volatility becomes,

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + \exp^{r(T-t)} a^2 S^2 V_{SS}).$$

Barle and Soner proved the existence of the viscosity solution of for the European options with this very volatility in their paper. Also showed that the numerical results have significant difference between the classical Black-Scholes model and the nonlinear model with transaction cost.

5.10 Risk adjusted Pricing Volatility Model

Kratka[15] came up with this model. Later Jandacka and Sevcovic [43] advanced this model. The optimal time trail δt between the transactions is constructed to reduce the sum of the rate of the transaction costs and the rate of the risk from the

unprotected portfolio. In this way the portfolio is still well protected with the Risk adjusted Pricing Methodology(RAPM) and the improved volatility is,

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + 3(\frac{C^2 M}{2\pi} SV_{SS})^{1/3}).$$

Here $M \geq 0$ is the transaction cost measure and $C \geq 0$ is the risk premium measure.

5.11 Analytical Solution

We solve (5.2) subject to the terminal and boundary conditions . We change the variables [?, 24],

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \ln\left(\frac{S}{K}\right), \\ \tau &= \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2(T - t), \\ u(x, \tau) &= e^{-x} \frac{V(S, t)}{K}. \end{aligned}$$

Differentiation gives,

$$\begin{aligned} V_t &= u_\tau \tau_t S = -\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S u_\tau, \\ V_S &= u_x x_S S + u = u_x + u, \\ V_{SS} &= u_{xx} x_S + u_x x_S = \frac{1}{S}(u_{xx} + u_x). \end{aligned}$$

Plugging these values into (5.2) ;we get,

$$-\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S u_\tau + \frac{1}{2}\tilde{\sigma}^2 S(u_{xx} + u_x) + rS(u_x + u) - ruS = 0.$$

Now we are going to multiply by $-\frac{2}{S\tilde{\sigma}^2}$

$$u_\tau - \frac{\tilde{\sigma}^2}{\sigma^2}(u_{xx} + u_x) - Du_x = 0.$$

Where $D = \frac{2r}{\tilde{\sigma}^2}$ and $\tilde{\sigma}^2$ depends on the volatility model. $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $0 \leq \tau \leq \frac{\sigma^2 T}{2}$ Now we plug in the volatility models:

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + Le.sign(u_{xx} + u_x))$$

or,

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + \Psi(e^{\frac{2r\tau}{\sigma^2}} aK e^x(u_{xx} + u_x)))$$

or,

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + (e^{\frac{2r\tau}{\sigma^2}} aK e^x (u_{xx} + u_x)))$$

or,

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + 3(\frac{C^2 M}{2\pi}(u_{xx} + u_x))^{1/3}).$$

5.12 Conclusion

In this chapter , we have discussed fairly about the different volatility models. We have given short descriptions of the famous volatility models. This chapter ended with the analytical solution of the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Model. This solution has similarities with the Linear one.

Chapter 6

Numerical Investigation of Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation

There are numerous numerical methods for solving Black-Scholes equation for European, American and Asian options. We can also solve linear Black-Scholes model using numerical methods. But there are major difference between the same numerical method as the volatility becomes a variable. We show the process and some different approaches to solve the volatility term. Also the volatility term is defined as different functions because of the nonlinearity.

We have already showed in the previous chapters that there are exact solution for European call and put options. But if we seek more accurate answer which matches with the reality, we have to dug a bit deeper which eventually gives us the nonlinear Black-Scholes equations with various volatility models. For these complicated contracts in general settings, analytical formulae are seldom available and numerical methods have to used to solve the problem. These Methods are different from lattice methods which includes binomial and trinomial approximations [18], Monte Carlo methods using the least-square techniques [42], analytical approximations [1, 14, 52], finite-element discretizations [74, 47] to finite-difference methods [2, 13, 17].

We have another classical method which consists of developing of the free boundary problem into a linear complementary problem (LCP) and the solution by the Projected Successive Over Relaxation (PSOR) method of Cryer [20]. And there was another method developed called penalty and front-fixing [55]. The underlying model changes which is a disadvantage in these methods.

A complete different procedure which is based on a recursive calculation[37] of the early exercise boundary, estimating the boundary only at some points and then approximating the whole boundary by Richardson extrapolation. Explicit boundary tracking algorithms which are a finite-difference bisection scheme [49] or the front-tracking strategy of Han and Wu [33].

Our numerical investigation is solely focused on finite difference schemes. We give a detailed analysis on this scheme.

6.1 European Call option

We are going to use finite-difference schemes to solve the converted partial differential equation (PDE) of *Black-Scholes Equation*,

$$u_\tau - \frac{\tilde{\sigma}^2}{\sigma^2}(u_{xx} + u_x) - Du_x = 0. \quad (6.1)$$

Where $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $0 \leq \tau \leq \tilde{T}$ with the respective volatilities (5.2) subject to the initial and boundary conditions,

$$u(x, 0) = (1 - e^{-x})^+ \quad \text{for } x \in \mathbb{R},$$

$$u(x, \tau) = 0 \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow \infty,$$

$$u(x, \tau) \approx 1 - e^{-D\tau - x} \quad \text{as } x \rightarrow \infty.$$

We are going to give a introduction to finite difference schemes and then present the numerical results from **MATLAB**.

6.2 Finite-Difference Methods

The main goal of finite-difference schemes is to approximate the derivatives of the difference quotients and the solution of the emerging discrete schemes.

At first, we start by discretizing the domain of the converted Partial differential Equation (PDE) of **Black Scholes Equation** with the respective volatilities. Then

we are going to replace the derivatives by appropriate difference quotients. Then our investigation using finite-difference continues in terms of convergence. We introduce classical finite-difference schemes for the European Call option.

6.3 Grid

We are going to transform the spatial domain and the time domain.

Now $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\tau \in [0, \tilde{T}]$ by a bounded interval $x \in [-R, R], R > 0$. Now we discretize the new computational domain by a uniform grid (x_i, τ_n) with $x_i = ih$ and $\tau_n = nk$, where $h > 0$ is the spatial step, and $k > 0$ is the time step. And $i \in [-N, N], -R = -Nh, R = Nh, n \in [0, M]$ and $\tilde{T} = Mk$.

We denote the approximate solution of the partial differential equation of **Black-Scholes** in x_i at time τ_n by

$$U_i^n \approx u(x_i, \tau_n).$$

And discretize the initial and boundary conditions in the following way:

$$U_i^0 = (1 - e^{-ih})^+,$$

$$U_{-N}^n = 0,$$

$$U_N^n = 1 - e^{-Dnk - Nh}.$$

Now for a more fitting treatment of the unbounded spatial domain $x \in \mathbb{R}$, we are going to introduce **artificial boundary conditions** [26] to confine the unbounded domain to a bounded computational domain.

6.4 Difference Quotients

The spatial derivative can be approximated with *forward differences*:

$$u_x(x, \tau) = \frac{u(x+h, \tau) - u(x, \tau)}{h} + O(h).$$

or *backward differences*:

$$u_x(x, \tau) = \frac{u(x, \tau) - u(x-h, \tau)}{h} + O(h).$$

We can sum these differences which results in central differences and we get:

$$u_x(x, \tau) = \frac{u(x+h, \tau) - u(x-h, \tau)}{2h} + O(h^2).$$

For the second spatial derivative we compute using the Taylor formula:

$$u_{xx}(x_i, \tau_n) = \frac{u(x+h, \tau) - 2u(x, \tau) + u(x-h, \tau)}{h^2} + O(h^2).$$

Now we can call back that a function $f(h)$ is in $O(h^r)$, if there exists a constant $M > 0$, such that $|f(h)| \leq M |h^r|$ as $h \rightarrow 0$. It means that the quantity $f(h)$ is bounded by a constant multiple of h^r for sufficiently small h [70]. We call the error between differential quotient and difference quotient the **truncation error**.

To discretize the partial derivatives of the **transformed Black-Scholes Equation**, we are going to introduce the following notation for the forward difference quotient with the spatial step size h :

$$D_h^+ U_i^n = \frac{U_{i+1}^n - U_i^n}{h} \approx u_x(x_i, \tau_n).$$

and we leave out the error term $O(h)$.

Similarly the **backward difference** quotient with respect to the spatial variable is denoted as:

$$D_h^- U_i^n = \frac{U_i^n - U_{i-1}^n}{h} \approx u_x(x_i, \tau_n).$$

So the **central difference** quotient is:

$$D_h^0 U_i^n = \frac{U_{i+1}^n - U_{i-1}^n}{2h} \approx u_x(x_i, \tau_n).$$

where *truncation error* of $O(h)$ and $O(h^2)$ are omitted.

Now for the *second spatial* derivative we introduce the standard difference quotient:

$$D_h^2 U_i^n = \frac{U_{i+1}^n - 2U_i^n + U_{i-1}^n}{h^2} \approx u_{xx}(x_i, \tau_n).$$

Where the error term is $O(h^2)$. The central differences in the time variable are never used in practice because they always lead the way to bad numerical schemes, which are inherently not stable [76]. Now using the schemes results into a system of equations that can be written in a matrix form:

$$A^n U^{n+1} = B^n U^n + d^n. \tag{6.2}$$

where

$$U^n = (U_{-N+1}^n, \dots, U_0^n, \dots, U_{N-1}^n)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2N-1}.$$

$$A^n = \begin{pmatrix} a_0 & a_1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ a_{-1} & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & a_1 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & a_{-1} & a_0 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(2N-1) \times (2N-1)}.$$

$$B^n = \begin{pmatrix} b_0 & b_1 & b_2 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ b_{-1} & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & & 0 \\ b_{-2} & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & b_2 \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & b_1 \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & b_{-2} & b_{-1} & b_0 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(2N-1) \times (2N-1)}.$$

$$d^n = \begin{pmatrix} b_{-2}U_{-N-1}^n + b_{-1}U_{-N}^n - a_{-1}U_{-N}^{n+1} \\ b_{-2}U_{-N}^n \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ b_2U_N^n \\ b_1U_N^n + b_2U_{N+1}^n - a_1U_N^{n+1} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(2N-1) \times (2N-1)}.$$

Now the matrix A^n is tridiagonal. Hence the resulting systems can be solved with linear effort $O(N)$ using the Thomas algorithm [71, 33]. This is completed by first decomposing the matrix $A^n = L^n R^n$ into a lower and an upper bidiagonal matrix and secondly solving $L^n R^n U^{n+1} = B^n U^n + d^n$ by forward and backward substitution. Hence, we solve $L^n Y^n = B^n U^n + d^n$ for Y^n and after that we solve $R^n U^{n+1} = Y^n$ for U^{n+1} .

We need U_{-N-1}^n and U_{N+1}^n for the vector d^n . But these values are not in the grid points that are taken into account. They are the points before and after the boundary

conditions. We define the auxiliary or ghost boundary conditions [70],

$$U_{-N-1}^n = 0 \text{ and } U_{N+1}^n = 1 - e^{-Dnk-(N+1)h}. \quad (6.3)$$

And after this, we are going to assume that,

$$\sum_{i=-1}^1 a_i = \sum_{i=-2}^2 b_i = 1.$$

This is satisfied by any consistent scheme after normalization of the coefficients [61].

6.5 Volatility Models

We can deal with the derivatives in the volatility in different ways. We can write the modified volatility as,

$$\tilde{\sigma}^2 = \sigma^2(1 + s(x, \tau)).$$

Here $s(x, \tau)$ denotes the **volatility correction** in x at time τ . And term depends on the first and second spatial derivatives of u . In the paper of Daring[25], he proposes a smoother approximation of u_{xx} for the *volatility correction* by choosing:

$$u_{xx}(x_i, \tau_n) \approx \frac{U_{i+2}^n - 2U_i^n + U_{i-2}^n}{4h^2} = D_{2h}^2 U_i^n.$$

Here we have truncation error of order $O(h^2)$. We deal with the nonlinearity explicitly in all the schemes.

Then, from **Leland's Model**:

$$s_i^n = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{\kappa}{\sigma \sqrt{\delta t}} \text{sign}(D_{2h}^2 U_i^n + D_h^0 U_i^n).$$

Barles' and Soner's model's volatility correction is :

$$s_i^n = \Psi(e^{D\tau_n+x_i} a^2 K(D_{2h}^2 U_i^n + D_h^0 U_i^n)).$$

Then volatility correction for the case when $\Psi(\cdot)$ is considered as the **identity** is:

$$s_i^n = e^{D\tau_n+x_i} a^2 K(D_{2h}^2 U_i^n + D_h^0 U_i^n).$$

Lastly the volatility correction for the Risk Adjusted Pricing Mthedology(**RAPM**) is:

$$s_i^n = 3 \left(\frac{C^2 M}{2\pi} (D_{2h}^2 U_i^n + D_h^0 U_i^n) \right)^{1/3}.$$

There is a complication with the evaluation of s_i^n at the boundary, as in the theory we require $U^n \in \mathbb{R}^{2N+3}$ to have the ability to calculate s_{N-1}^n and s_{-N+1}^n . But this calculation demands the need of U_{-N-1}^n and U_{N+1}^n , which are outside the domain. During's paper [25] has the statement that the impact of the nonlinearity at the boundary is not that significant and it can be neglected for large R . So we can assume that our **auxiliary or ghost** boundary conditions are valid and say that:

$$s^n = (s_{-N+1}^n, \dots, s_0^n, \dots, s_{N-1}^n)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2N-1}.$$

6.6 Existence and Convergence

Our desire is to give a logical approximation for the sequence of the solutions of

$$A^n U^{n+1} = B^n U^n + d^n.$$

Then these needs to be satisfied:

1. A uniform solution U^n has to exist for each $n \in [0, M - 1]$.
2. And U_i^n has to converge towards the exact solution of

$$u_\tau - \frac{\tilde{\sigma}^2}{\sigma^2} (u_{xx} + u_x) - D u_x = 0,$$

as $k \rightarrow 0$ and $h \rightarrow 0$.

We are going to callback the terms and conditions of the existence and convergence for the **linear** case. In which case the *volatility correction* s_i^n is equal to **zero** and Hence $A^n = A, B^n = B$ and the coefficients of d^n are constants.

A uniform solution to the system of equations exists [41], if the matrix A is regular(a regular matrix A is described as a square matrix that for all positive integer n , is such that A^n has positive entries.). The scheme (2) converges, if its consistent and stable. Hence, we describe the terms **consistency** and **stability**.

- **Consistency**

A scheme $L_{h,k}$ of order (a, b) is consistent, if there exists a constant $M > 0$ such that,

$$\max_{i,n} |L_{h,k}u_i^n| \leq M(k^a + h^b)$$

for sufficiently small $h, k > 0$. In here, u_i^n is the exact solution to (1) in (x_i, τ_n) and $L_{h,k}$ is the finite difference scheme that excludes the truncation error of order $O(k^a + h^b)$.

- **Stability**

To establish stability of (2), we are going to take into account computer evaluated vector including the rounding errors \hat{U}^n . So

$$A\hat{U}^{n+1} = B\hat{U}^n + d^n + r^n.$$

where r^n denotes the rounding errors. The error vector is,

$$e^n = \hat{U}^n - U^n,$$

acts in according to

$$Ae^{n+1} = Be^n + r^n.$$

To simplify this ,we are going to assume that $e^0 \neq 0$ which means that there is already a rounding error when evaluating the initial condition. Simultaneously, we are going to assume that the matrix vector multiplication to obtain U^{n+1} works precisely, So

$$r^n = 0 \quad n \in [0, M - 1].$$

We have the error:

$$e^{n+1} = A^{-1}Be^n = (A^{-1}B)^2e^{n-1} = \dots = (A^{-1}B)^{n+1}e^0.$$

For us to have a stable system, preceding errors have to be damped and therefore we need

$$(A^{-1}B)^{n+1}e^0 \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

We are going to use a *Lemma 6.7* from [74]. The requirement is equivalent to the absolute value of the eigenvalues of $A^{-1}B$ being less than 1. Therefore, for the linear case, a scheme is stable, if

$$\rho(A^{-1}B) = \max(|\zeta| : \zeta \text{ is eigenvalue of } A^{-1}B) < 1.$$

If these statements are true, then we have a reasonable approximation to the linear system (2). In case the solution to the (2) has small oscillations, is completely dependent on the dissipation.

Any scheme is called non oscillatory or dissipative, if the eigenvalues ζ of $A^{-1}B$ satisfy an inequality of the form of:

$$|\zeta| \leq 1 - p |ih|^{2q},$$

where $|ih| \leq \pi$, for some real constant $p > 0$ and $q \in \mathbb{N}$.

These oscillations are not because of instability, because of not having adequate resolution [60].

These statements are true for the linear case which means when $s_i^n = 0$. But for the second case which is nonlinear, $s_i^n \neq 0$, these terms are difficult to state and prove for arbitrary schemes and arbitrary coefficients in A^n, B^n and d^n . One of the approaches is to preserve the coefficients in (2) by assuming them to be constant at each point (x_i, τ_n) and check stability. It is well known that for linear parabolic problems with variable coefficients a lenient strengthening of the **local stability** is adequate to secure overall stability [60]. Now for the second case of nonlinearity, the limitations of what can be proved generally are gained quickly. We investigate the nonlinear case numerically in the next sections and finite-difference schemes for the European Call option are going to be introduced.

We define some parameters for further calculations:

$$\lambda = -(1 + D), \quad \alpha = \frac{\lambda h}{2}, \quad r = \frac{k}{h^2}, \quad \mu = \frac{k}{h}.$$

6.7 Explicit Method(Forward-Time Central Space)

We are going to replace the derivatives in the converted **Black-Scholes** PDE for the European Call Option by proper finite-difference quotients. Hence equation (6.1) can be rewritten as:

$$u_\tau = (1 + s)(u_{xx} + u_x) + Du_x = s(u_{xx} + u_x) + (1 + D)u_x + u_{xx}. \quad (6.4)$$

Here s the continuous *volatility correction* relying on the Volatility model.

For the case of **explicit method**, the time derivative is approximated by $D_k^+ U_i^n$, the first spatial derivative by $D_h^0 U_i^n$, and the second spatial derivative by both $D_h^2 U_i^n$ and $D_{2h}^2 U_i^n$. We leave the error terms of order $O(k + h^2)$. Therefore, the scheme is of order (1, 2). We are going to replace the derivatives by the respective finite-difference quotients ,we get:

$$D_k^+ U_i^n = s_i^n (D_{2h}^2 U_i^n + D_h^0 U_i^n) + (1 + D) D_h^0 U_i^n + D_h^2 U_i^n. \quad (6.5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{U_i^{n+1} - U_i^n}{k} &= s_i^n \left(\frac{U_{i+2}^n - 2U_i^n + U_{i-2}^n}{4h^2} + \frac{U_{i+1}^n - U_{i-1}^n}{2h} \right) \\ &+ (1 + D) \frac{U_{i+1}^n - U_{i-1}^n}{2h} + \frac{U_{i+1}^n - 2U_i^n + U_{i-1}^n}{h^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Which is analogous to,

$$\begin{aligned} U_i^{n+1} &= U_i^n + k s_i^n \left(\frac{U_{i+2}^n - 2U_i^n + U_{i-2}^n}{4h^2} + \frac{U_{i+1}^n - U_{i-1}^n}{2h} \right) + k(1 + D) \frac{U_{i+1}^n - U_{i-1}^n}{2h} \\ &+ k \frac{U_{i+1}^n - 2U_i^n + U_{i-1}^n}{h^2} \\ &= \frac{k s_i^n}{4h^2} U_{i-2}^n + \left(\frac{k}{h^2} - \frac{k(1 + D + s_i^n)}{2h} \right) U_{i-1}^n + \left(1 - \frac{k(s_i^n + 4)}{2h^2} \right) U_i^n + \\ &\left(\frac{k(1 + D + s_i^n)}{2h} + \frac{k}{h^2} \right) U_{i+1}^n + \frac{k s_i^n}{4h^2} U_{i+2}^n. \end{aligned}$$

We are going to write this scheme for $i \in [-N, N]$ which resolves in the system of equations with the matrix coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{-1} &= 0, \\
a_0 &= 1, \\
a_1 &= 0, \\
b_{-2} &= \frac{ks_i^n}{4h^2}, \\
b_{-1} &= \frac{k}{h^2} - \frac{k(1 + D + s_i^n)}{2h}, \\
b_0 &= 1 - \frac{k(s_i^n + 4)}{2h^2}, \\
b_1 &= \frac{k(1 + D + s_i^n)}{2h} + \frac{k}{h^2}, \\
b_2 &= \frac{ks_i^n}{4h^2}.
\end{aligned}$$

Redefining the coefficients by the set of predefined parameters:

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{-1} &= 0, \\
a_0 &= 1, \\
a_1 &= 0, \\
b_{-2} &= \frac{rs_i^n}{4}, \\
b_{-1} &= r + \frac{\mu(\lambda - s_i^n)}{2}, \\
b_0 &= 1 - \frac{k(s_i^n + 4)}{2h^2}, \\
b_1 &= r + \frac{\mu(s_i^n - \lambda)}{2}, \\
b_2 &= \frac{rs_i^n}{4}.
\end{aligned}$$

As stated by the stability requirement for the linear case [70], we want to have the necessary stability condition,

$$r \leq \frac{1}{2}.$$

And the solution is non-oscillatory for the linear case if:

$$|\alpha| \leq 1.$$

6.8 Implicit Method (Backward Time-Central Time)

The Implicit finite-difference Method gives us:

$$D_k^- U_i^{n+1} = s_i^n (D_{2h}^2 U_i^n + D_h^0 U_i^n) + (1 + D) D_h^0 U_i^{n+1} + D_h^2 U_i^{n+1}. \quad (6.6)$$

or,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{U_i^{n+1} - U_i^n}{k} &= s_i^n \left(\frac{U_{i+2}^n - 2U_i^n + U_{i-2}^n}{4h^2} + \frac{U_{i+1}^n - U_{i-1}^n}{2h} \right) \\ &+ (1 + D) \frac{U_{i+1}^{n+1} - U_{i-1}^{n+1}}{2h} + \frac{U_{i+1}^{n+1} - 2U_i^{n+1} + U_{i-1}^{n+1}}{h^2}. \end{aligned}$$

It has the error of order (1, 2). After some calculations, we get the following matrix coefficients,

$$\begin{aligned} a_{-1} &= \frac{k(1 + D)}{2h} - \frac{k}{h^2}, \\ a_0 &= 1 + \frac{2k}{h^2}, \\ a_1 &= -\frac{k(1 + D)}{2h} - \frac{k}{h^2}, \\ b_{-2} &= \frac{ks_i^n}{4h^2}, \\ b_{-1} &= -\frac{k(s_i^n)}{2h}, \\ b_0 &= 1 - \frac{ks_i^n}{2h^2}, \\ b_1 &= \frac{ks_i^n}{2h}, \\ b_2 &= \frac{ks_i^n}{4h^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Or, using our defined parameters,

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{-1} &= \frac{\lambda\mu}{2} - r, \\
a_0 &= 1 + \frac{2k}{h^2}, \\
a_1 &= -\frac{\lambda\mu}{2} - r, \\
b_{-2} &= \frac{rs_i^n}{4}, \\
b_{-1} &= -\frac{\mu s_i^n}{2}, \\
b_0 &= 1 - \frac{rs_i^n}{2}, \\
b_1 &= \frac{\mu s_i^n}{2}, \\
b_2 &= \frac{rs_i^n}{4}.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, from [70], it is unconditionally stable and non-oscillatory in the linear case if

$$|\alpha| \leq 1.$$

is satisfied.

6.9 Crank-Nicolson

This traditional finite-difference scheme has better accuracy than Explicit and Implicit Methods because of its higher order of (2, 2) [70]. Actually, we average the forward and backward difference methods by summing them up which improves the order and stability. But, in this method we approach the second spatial derivative by $D_h^2 U_i^n$ except in the nonlinear volatility term s_i^n .

We are going to replace all the derivatives by their corresponding finite-difference quotients:

$$D_k^+ U_i^n + D_k^- U_i^{n+1} = s_i^n (D_h^2 U_i^n + D_h^0 U_i^n) + s_i^n (D_h^2 U_i^{n+1} + D_h^0 U_i^{n+1}) \quad (6.7)$$

$$+ (1 + D)(D_h^0 U_i^n + D_h^0 U_i^{n+1}) + D_h^2 U_i^n + D_h^2 U_i^{n+1}. \quad (6.8)$$

This is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{U_i^{n+1} - U_i^n}{k} &= \frac{s_i^n}{2} \left(\frac{U_{i+1}^n - 2U_i^n + U_{i-1}^n}{h^2} + \frac{U_{i+1}^n - U_{i-1}^n}{2h} \right) \\ &+ \frac{s_i^n}{2} \left(\frac{U_{i+1}^{n+1} - 2U_i^{n+1} + U_{i-1}^{n+1}}{h^2} + \frac{U_{i+1}^{n+1} - U_{i-1}^{n+1}}{2h} \right) \\ &+ (1 + D) \frac{U_{i+1}^n - U_{i-1}^n + U_{i+1}^{n+1} - U_{i-1}^{n+1}}{4h} \\ &+ \frac{U_{i+1}^n - 2U_i^n + U_{i-1}^n + U_{i+1}^{n+1} - 2U_i^{n+1} + U_{i-1}^{n+1}}{2h^2}. \end{aligned}$$

The coefficients of the matrix:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{-1} &= s_i^n \left(\frac{-r}{2} + \frac{\mu}{4} \right) - \frac{r}{2} - \frac{\lambda\mu}{4}, \\ a_0 &= 1 + r(1 + s_i^n), \\ a_1 &= s_i^n \left(-\frac{r}{2} - \frac{\mu}{4} \right) - \frac{r}{2} + \frac{\lambda\mu}{4}, \\ b_{-1} &= s_i^n \left(\frac{r}{2} - \frac{\mu}{4} \right) + \frac{r}{2} + \frac{\lambda\mu}{4}, \\ b_0 &= 1 - r(1 + s_i^n), \\ b_1 &= s_i^n \left(\frac{r}{2} + \frac{\mu}{4} \right) + \frac{r}{2} - \frac{\lambda\mu}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

This scheme is unconditionally stable in the linear case [70].

6.10 Graphical Representation

Now for the **European Call Option price** for the following parameters:

$$\sigma = 0.2, \quad K = 100, \quad T = 1, \quad R = 1,$$

$$r = 0.1, \quad h = 0.1, \quad k = 0.0001.$$

(a) RAPM model ($M = .01$, $C = 30$).

(b) Barles' and Soner's model ($a = .02$).

(c) $\psi(x) = x$ selected as the Identity ($a = .02$).

(d) Leland's model ($\delta t = .01$, $\kappa = .05$).

Figure 6.1: Value of European Call Option price $V(S, t)$ of Nonlinear Black-Scholes models for various volatility models for spatial step $h = .1$ and time step $k = .0001$ with the Crank-Nicolson Method.

The impact of transaction costs which are modeled by the volatilities and evaluated with the Crank-Nicolson finite difference scheme can be seen in the next figure, we plot the difference between the European Call Option price with

$$V_{nonlinear}(S, t) - V_{linear}(S, t).$$

transaction costs and the European Call Option price without the transaction costs. We get a significant price deviation between the classical (linear) Black-Scholes Model and the nonlinear model.

(a) $\psi(x) = x$ selected as the Identity ($a = .02$).

(b) Barles' and Soner's model ($a = .02$).

(c) RAPM model ($M = .01$, $C = 30$).

(d) Leland's model ($\delta t = .01$, $\kappa = .05$).

Figure 6.2: The impact of transaction costs Nonlinear $V_{nonlinear}(S, t) - V_{linear}(S, t)$ with the Crank-Nicolson Method.

The difference that we have is not symmetric for all the transaction cost models. But decreases closer to the expiry date. And this is the expected result. We have plotted all the nonlinear models with the linear model in figure (6.3). Now for each volatility model and each difference scheme, we compare the deviation of accuracy of the above computation at $t = 0$. We use the infinity norm l^∞ . If we reduce the spatial step size to $h = .001$ or $h = .0001$, it improves the accuracy considerably. However, it increases the computational time monumentally. The deviation from the linear model is evaluated only for the stock price $S(t) = 269$ at $t = 0$. We can see the difference between the Models from the table.

Volatility Model	Deviation from the linear model $s_i^n = 0$
Identity	.00068
Leland	.02945
RAPM	.03813

Table 6.1: l^∞ deviation for different volatility models for the stock price $S(t) = 269$ at $t = 0$.

Figure 6.3: Value of European Call Option price $V(S, 0)$ for different volatility models vs the linear model with the Crank-Nicolson Method.

The plot (6.3) shows the price of a European Call option for $V(S, 0)$ that is at $t = 0$, and how all the transaction cost models converge. We have given the algorithms for explicit and implicit methods too. We use them to implement them into MATLAB too. At first we plot the European Call Option price $V(S, t)$ for different volatility models in Implicit Method. Then we give a Nonlinear Vs Linear graph similar to the Crank-Nicolson in implicit method. We repeat this for explicit method too. They give the same resemblance with the Crank-Nicolson graphs. But Crank-Nicolson gives better numerical results.

(a) $\psi(x) = x$ selected as the Identity ($a = .02$).

(b) Barles' and Soner's model ($a = .02$).

(c) RAPM model ($M = .01, C = 30$).

(d) Leland's model ($\delta t = .01, \kappa = .05$).

Figure 6.4: Value of European Call Option price $V(S, t)$ of Nonlinear Black-Scholes models for various volatility models for spatial step $h = .1$ and time step $k = .001$ with the Implicit Method.

Figure 6.5: The Identity model $\psi(x) = x$ with parameter ($a = .02$) for the $(V_{nonlinear}(S, t) - V_{linear}(S, t))$ plot for spatial step $h = .1$ and time step $k = .001$ with the Implicit Method.

(a) $\psi(x) = x$ selected as the Identity ($a = .02$).

(b) Barles' and Soner's model ($a = .02$).

(c) RAPM model ($M = .01, C = 30$).

(d) Leland's model ($\delta t = .01, \kappa = .05$).

Figure 6.6: Value of European Call Option price $V(S, t)$ of Nonlinear Black-Scholes models for various volatility models for spatial step $h = .1$ and time step $k = .00001$ with the Explicit Method.

Figure 6.7: The Identity model $\psi(x) = x$ with parameter ($a = .02$) for the $(V_{nonlinear}(S, t) - V_{linear}(S, t))$ plot for spatial step $h = .1$ and time step $k = .001$ with the Explicit Method.

6.11 Conclusion

We have thoroughly investigated the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation numerically. At first we show how the Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation can be represented as system of equations. We use matrices instead of System of equations. Then we give graphical representation of the solution in implicit, explicit and Crank-Nicolson Method. We give a Comparison between the different transaction cost modeled by volatilities.

Chapter 7

Fractional Black-Scholes Equation

7.1 Introduction

In quantitative finance, option pricing is a major problem. There are models other than Black-Scholes model for pricing options which give better results; one such model is known as Finite Moment Log Stable (FMLS) which can be put in writing as fractional diffusion class equation [40]. Fractional Calculus is the calculus of the differentiation and integration where the order is a fractional number [56]. We seek to discover the analytical solution of Black-Scholes Equation's Fractional Derivatives by the use of Adomian Decomposition Method.

7.2 Transformed Black-Scholes Equation

Here, we recall from the second chapter where the analytical solution of Linear Black-Scholes Equation was given. Let $V(S, t)$ be the option price, then

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + rS \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} - rV = 0. \quad (7.1)$$

Having the initial and boundary conditions which are:

$$V(0, \tau) = 0,$$

$$V(S, \tau) \approx S, \text{ as } S \rightarrow \infty,$$

$$V(S, T) = \max(S - K, 0).$$

Here, we have K is the strike price, σ is the volatility, T is the expiry time and r is the risk free interest rate. Then we apply changes to the variables:

$$\begin{aligned} S &= Ke^x, \\ t &= T - \frac{\tau}{(1/2)\sigma^2}, \\ V &= Kv(x, t). \end{aligned}$$

Which gives us the

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + (k - 1) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - kv,$$

where $k = \frac{2r}{\sigma^2}$. Now The initial condition is:

$$v(x, 0) = \max(e^x - 1, 0).$$

7.3 Fractional Derivative

The most common fractional Derivatives are:

Caputo: The fractional derivative of $g(x)$ is defined as [58]:

$$D^\beta g(x) = K^{n-\beta} D^n g(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\beta)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{n-\beta-1} g^n(t) dt.$$

for $n-1 < \beta \leq n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $x > 0$.

Mittag-Leffler Function: This function $M_\beta(x)$ is defined as [54]:

$$M_\beta(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^j}{\Gamma(\beta j + 1)},$$

where $\beta > 0$ and $x \in \mathbb{C}$.

7.4 Fractional Black-Scholes Equation of Time

Here, we assess the fractional Black-Scholes Equation for time [40]:

$$\frac{\partial^\beta v}{\partial \tau^\beta} = \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + (k - 1) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - kv, \quad 0 < \beta \leq 1. \quad (7.2)$$

It has the initial condition $v(x, 0) = e^x - 1$, $x > 0$. Adomian Decomposition Method is used in the equation (7.2) to get:

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial^{1-\beta}}{\partial \tau^{1-\beta}} \left[\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + (k - 1) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - kv \right].$$

We are going to integrate on the both sides with respect to τ to get:

$$v(x, \tau) = v(x, 0) + \int_0^\tau \left(\frac{\partial^{1-\beta}}{\partial s^{1-\beta}} \left[\frac{\partial^2 v(x, s)}{\partial x^2} + (k-1) \frac{\partial v(x, s)}{\partial x} - kv(x, s) \right] \right) ds.$$

We denote $v(x, 0) = v_0$. Then

$$v(x, \tau) = \int_0^\tau \left(\frac{\partial^{1-\beta}}{\partial s^{1-\beta}} \left[\frac{\partial^2 v_0(x, s)}{\partial x^2} + (k-1) \frac{\partial v_0(x, s)}{\partial x} - kv_0(x, s) \right] \right) ds.$$

The repetitive method yields for $m > 1$

$$v_m(x, \tau) = \int_0^\tau \left(\frac{\partial^{1-\beta}}{\partial s^{1-\beta}} \left[\frac{\partial^2 v_{m-1}(x, s)}{\partial x^2} + (k-1) \frac{\partial v_{m-1}(x, s)}{\partial x} - kv_{m-1}(x, s) \right] \right) ds. \quad (7.3)$$

Therefore from **Adomian Decomposition Method**, we have the solution of (7.2) by

$$v(x, \tau) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} v_m(x, \tau).$$

We are going to use the initial condition:

$$v(x, 0) = e^x - 1, \quad x > 0.$$

So,

$$v_0 = e^x - 1.$$

From (7.3), we evaluate the rest of the terms of the solution.

$$\begin{aligned} v_1(x, \tau) &= \int_0^\tau \left(\frac{\partial^{1-\beta}}{\partial s^{1-\beta}} \left[\frac{\partial^2 v_0}{\partial x^2} + (k-1) \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} - kv_0 \right] \right) ds. \\ &= -e^x \frac{-k\tau^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} + (e^x - 1) \frac{-k\tau^\beta}{\Gamma((\beta+1))} \\ v_2(x, \tau) &= \int_0^\tau \left(\frac{\partial^{1-\beta}}{\partial s^{1-\beta}} \left[\frac{\partial^2 v_1(x, 0)}{\partial x^2} + (k-1) \frac{\partial v_1(x, 0)}{\partial x} - kv_1(x, 0) \right] \right) ds. \\ &= -e^x \frac{(-k\tau^\beta)^2}{\Gamma(2\beta+1)} + (e^x - 1) \frac{(-k\tau^\beta)^2}{\Gamma((2\beta+1))} \\ v_3(x, \tau) &= \int_0^\tau \left(\frac{\partial^{1-\beta}}{\partial s^{1-\beta}} \left[\frac{\partial^2 v_2(x, 0)}{\partial x^2} + (k-1) \frac{\partial v_2(x, 0)}{\partial x} - kv_2(x, 0) \right] \right) ds. \\ &= -e^x \frac{(-k\tau^\beta)^3}{\Gamma(3\beta+1)} + (e^x - 1) \frac{(-k\tau^\beta)^3}{\Gamma((3\beta+1))}. \end{aligned}$$

So, the solution of the equation (7.2) by the Adomian Decomposition Method,

$$\begin{aligned}
v(x, \tau) &= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} v_m(x, \tau) \\
&= e^x \left(\frac{-k\tau^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} - \frac{(-k\tau^\beta)^2}{\Gamma(2\beta+1)} + \frac{(-k\tau^\beta)^3}{\Gamma(3\beta+1)} - \dots \right) \\
&\quad + (e^x - 1) \left(1 - \frac{-k\tau^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} + \frac{(-k\tau^\beta)^2}{\Gamma(2\beta+1)} + \dots \right) \\
&= e^x (1 - M_\beta(-k\tau^\beta)) + (e^x - 1) M_\beta(-k\tau^\beta) \\
&= e^x - M_\beta(-k\tau^\beta).
\end{aligned}$$

where $M_\beta(x)$ is called the Mittag-Leffler function of one parameter. $v(x, \tau) = e^x - M_\beta(-k\tau^\beta)$ is the exact solution of (7.2). And Mittag-Leffler function has the property [57, 46] when $\beta \rightarrow 1$, the solution (7.2) agrees with the exact solution of the Black-Scholes PDE.

7.5 Fractional Black-Scholes Equation of Space

Here, we consider the fractional Black-Scholes PDE for space [77]. In this case, we have fractional derivative in space. This is in the sense of Riemann-Liouville. The Levy density for a Log Stable is given below:

$$C_{LS}(x) = \begin{cases} Bq |x|^{-1-\beta} & x < 0, \\ Bpx^{-1-\beta} & x > 0. \end{cases}$$

Here $B > 0$, $p, q \in [-1, 1]$, $p + q = 1$ and $0 < \beta \leq 2$. We replace $p = 0$ and $q = 1$. Then this procedure converts into the well known Finite Moment Log Stable Method. The following fractional partial differential equation is given by (For European Option Price):

$$\frac{\partial V(x, \tau)}{\partial \tau} + \left(r + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^\beta \sec\left(\frac{\beta\pi}{2}\right) \right) \frac{\partial V(x, \tau)}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^\beta \sec\left(\frac{\beta\pi}{2}\right) \frac{\partial^\beta V(x, \tau)}{\partial_+ x^\beta} = rV(x, \tau) \quad (7.4)$$

Here $\frac{\partial^\beta V(x, \tau)}{\partial_+ x^\beta}$ is called the left Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative, r is risk-less interest rate and σ is volatility. Now, whenever $\beta \rightarrow 2$, (7.4) matches with Black-Scholes PDE.

We solve this very equation using Adomian Decomposition Method. At first, we set

$$V(x, 0) = e^x - 1.$$

We are going to write (7.4) as

$$\frac{\partial V(x, \tau)}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial^\beta V(x, \tau)}{\partial_+ x^\beta} - (r + sc) \frac{\partial V(x, \tau)}{\partial x} + rV(x, \tau).$$

Here $sc = \frac{1}{2}\sigma^\beta \sec(\frac{\beta\pi}{2})$ We are using integration on both sides with respect to τ to get:

$$V(x, \tau) = V(x, 0) + \int_0^\tau \left(sc \frac{\partial^\beta V(x, s)}{\partial_+ x^\beta} - (r + sc) \frac{\partial V(x, s)}{\partial x} + rV(x, s) \right) ds.$$

Let

$$V(x, 0) = V_0(x, 0).$$

Then

$$V_1(x, \tau) = V(x, 0) + \int_0^\tau \left(sc \frac{\partial^\beta V_0(x, s)}{\partial_+ x^\beta} - (r + sc) \frac{\partial V_0(x, s)}{\partial x} + rV_0(x, s) \right) ds.$$

And the rest of the terms can be evaluated by this repetitive process similar to the time fractional Black-Scholes section. And we get:

$$V_m(x, \tau) = \int_0^\tau \left(sc \frac{\partial^\beta V_{m-1}(x, s)}{\partial_+ x^\beta} - (r + sc) \frac{\partial V_{m-1}(x, s)}{\partial x} + rV_{m-1}(x, s) \right) ds. \quad (7.5)$$

Now, using Adomian Decomposition Method, the solution of this equation is:

$$V(x, \tau) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} V_m(x, \tau).$$

We have

$$V(x, 0) = e^x - 1 = V_0(x, \tau).$$

Then from (7.5), we evaluate the terms of the solution as:

$$\begin{aligned} V_1(x, \tau) &= \int_0^\tau \left(sc \frac{\partial^\beta V_0(x, t)}{\partial_+ x^\beta} - (r + sc) \frac{\partial V_0(x, t)}{\partial x} + rV_0(x, t) \right) dt \\ &= sc\tau \left[x^{3-\beta} M_{1,4-\beta}(x) + \frac{x^{2-\beta}}{\Gamma(3-\beta)} + \frac{x^{1-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} - M_{1,1}(x) \right] - r\tau \\ &= sc\tau [x^{1-\beta} M_{1,2-\beta} - M_{1,1}(x)] - r\tau. \end{aligned}$$

After that ,

$$\begin{aligned} V_2(x, \tau) &= \int_0^\tau \left(sc \frac{\partial^\beta V_1(x, t)}{\partial_+ x^\beta} - (r + sc) \frac{\partial V_1(x, t)}{\partial x} + rV_1(x, t) \right) dt \\ &= \frac{(sc\tau)^2}{2} [x^{-2\beta} (xM_{1,2-2\beta}(x) - M_{1,1-2\beta}(x)) \\ &\quad - x^{-1-\beta} (xM_{1,1-\beta}(x) - M_{1,\beta}(x))] - rsc\tau [x^{-2\beta} M_{1,1-2\beta}(x) \\ &\quad - x^{-1-\beta} M_{1,\beta}(x) - M_{1,2-\beta}(x) + M_{1,1}(x)]. \end{aligned}$$

And it goes on and on. Then the solution of (7.4) using the Adomian Decomposition Method is:

$$\begin{aligned}
V(x, \tau) &= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} V_m(x, \tau) \\
&= M_{1,1}(x) - 1 + sc\tau[x^{1-\beta}M_{1,2-\beta} - M_{1,1}(x)] - r\tau \\
&\quad + \frac{(sc\tau)^2}{2}[x^{-2\beta}(xM_{1,2-2\beta}(x) - M_{1,1-2\beta}(x)) \\
&\quad - x^{-1-\beta}(xM_{1,1-\beta}(x) - M_{1,\beta}(x))] - rsc\tau[x^{-2\beta}M_{1,1-2\beta}(x) \\
&\quad - x^{-1-\beta}M_{1,\beta}(x) - M_{1,2-\beta}(x) + M_{1,1}(x)] + \dots\dots\dots
\end{aligned}$$

Here $M_{a,b}(x)$ is known as the in general Mittag-Leffler function [57, 54]. We can use the Mittag-Leffler function property. We pick $sc = 1$, $r = -k$ and $\beta \rightarrow 2$, then almost all the terms get canceled and the solution matches with the exact solution of Black-Scholes PDE.

We could not implement Fractional Black-Scholes Equation in MATLAB because of the time scarcity.

7.6 Conclusion

We have briefly discussed about the Black-Scholes Equation with respect to fractional derivative. We do not have enough time to study this aspect of the Black-Scholes Equation. This will be included in the future work.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

This thesis work provides an overview of Linear Black-Scholes (LBS) and Nonlinear Black-Scholes (NLBS) Equation for European Options. Our main focus has been solving both linear and nonlinear equations numerically. We have investigated both Linear and Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation with adequate financial terminology. Spectral collocation method for LBS Equation has been implemented. Spectral collocation method is known for its exponential accuracy and computational scale. A big advantage in this method is that if we increase the grid points, the error decays exponentially. Then we use the Differential Quadrature Method on the LBS equation. There is a great resemblance between the Spectral Collocation and Differential Quadrature Method. We develop a Differential Quadrature Matrix which helped extensively in our numerical approximation. These two schemes provide a efficient and less time consuming approximation of the LBS equation. We provide the MATLAB implementations of the two schemes on Black-Scholes Equation. We compare the numerical results with the Exact solution. Then we introduce the NLBS Equation. We investigate several reasons for nonlinearity. We concentrate on several transaction models which include Leland's Model, Barles' and Soner's Model, the identity model and the risk adjusted pricing methodology. The analytical approach for the solution of NLBS Equation is given after that. Then we use Finite-Difference-Method (FDM) for the NLBS for European Options. We use implicit, explicit and Crank-Nicolson for the Nonlinear model For European Options. We show the numerical results from these schemes. Then we compare the transaction cost models to each other using the

FDM scheme with respect to the linear model. Fractional Black-Scholes Equation has been discussed briefly.

For future work, we want to carry on with our research on American and Asian options for LBS and NLBS equation. In addition, we want to implement Spectral Collocation Method for NLBS and fractional BS equation.

Our thesis work will provide a firm foundation for further numerical investigation on Linear and Nonlinear Black-Scholes Equation.

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